

CITAC NEWS

2026

TABLE OF CONTENTS

LETTER FROM THE EDITOR.....	4
FOREWORD BY THE CHAIR.....	6
ADDRESS OF THE VICE-CHAIR.....	8
THE DEMOCRATISATION OF THE EVALUATION OF THE MEASUREMENT UNCERTAINTY..	8
THE NEW EURACHEM/CITAC GUIDE ON “EVALUATION OF MEASUREMENT UNCERTAINTY FROM IN-HOUSE PRECISION AND RECOVERY DATA”.....	10
MESSAGE FROM THE CITAC SECRETARY.....	12
NEW MEMBERS.....	14
VASILISA BARANOVSKAYA.....	14
ELCIO CRUZ DE OLIVEIRA.....	15
TONGXIANG REN.....	17
SAMUEL TSZ-CHUN CHEUNG.....	18
LIAISON REPORTS.....	20
AFRIMETS ACTIVITIES.....	21
APMP ACTIVITIES.....	25
COOMET ACTIVITIES.....	28
EURAMET ACTIVITIES.....	35
SIM ACTIVITIES.....	39
IMEKO ACTIVITIES.....	45
ISO/TC 334 - REFERENCE MATERIALS.....	47
CITAC BEST PAPER AWARD 2025.....	50
Stable Isotope Reference Materials and Scale Definitions – Outcomes of the 2024 IAEA Experts Meeting.....	51
Activity Coefficients of HCl in Solutions Related to ‘Tris’ Buffers In Artificial Seawater. III. Tris Buffer + NaCl + H ₂ O, from 0.2 to 3.25 mol kg ⁻¹ Ionic Strength and from 5 °C to 45 °C	61
On the Role of Probability in Science, Analytical Measurement and QUAM.....	68

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LETTER FROM THE EDITOR

MESSAGE FROM THE EDITOR

Tang Lin Teo // Health Sciences Authority (HSA), Singapore

Dear Reader,

It is a pleasure to introduce you to this issue of the CITAC Newsletter. This edition is a special one for two reasons.

First, we are delighted to introduce several new members to the CITAC community. Their participation reflects both the continued relevance of our work and the growing recognition that traceability, comparability, and data integrity are important. We look forward to their perspectives and contributions as we collectively strengthen the foundations of reliable measurements.

Second, we are pleased to feature contributions from the recipients of the CITAC Best Paper Award, whose work exemplifies the depth and diversity of challenges our community is addressing. These papers reinforce a common theme:

robust measurement systems are built on strong reference frameworks, sound statistical thinking, and rigorous experimental science.

Finally, beyond the science, the year 2026 also marks an important moment for our community. After years of virtual engagement, we were pleased to reconvene in person for the first physical CITAC meeting since COVID-19, held on 18 April 2026 at Mercure Paris Boulogne Hotel. The discussions were candid, the exchanges energising, and the value of face-to-face interaction unmistakable. It was a timely reminder that while digital platforms have enabled continuity, collaboration is strengthened through direct engagement and shared purpose.

As we move forward, the expectations placed on analytical data will only continue to rise. Our role, collectively, is to ensure that the measurements underpinning decisions, whether in policy, healthcare, or industry, remain fit for purpose, defensible, and internationally trusted.

I would like to thank all contributors, award recipients, and members for the new and longstanding work in CITAC.

Warm regards,
Tang Lin Teo, Ph.D.
Editor, CITAC Newsletter

FOREWORD BY THE CHAIR

CITAC ACTIVITY IN 2025

Zoltan Mester // National Research Council (NRC), Canada

"Measurement underpins informed decision-making... providing the evidence base on which sound policy—and public trust—depend." (*World Metrology Day 2026 theme*)

As I complete my third year as CITAC Chair, it is clear that our community is not only maintaining but actively shaping global confidence in chemical measurements. Over 2025–2026, CITAC has delivered targeted guidance, strengthened its international role, and positioned itself at the centre of key developments in metrology in chemistry.

A central achievement was our collaboration with Eurachem on the new guide, *Evaluation of measurement uncertainty from in-house precision and recovery data*, to be formally presented in May 2026. This guide provides laboratories with a practical framework to derive uncertainty directly from internal validation data—addressing a longstanding gap between theory and routine practice. In parallel, we co-published the *IUPAC/CITAC guide: Interlaboratory comparison of categorical characteristics of a substance, material, or object* (I. Kuselman, T. Gadrich, F.R. Pennechi, et al., *Pure and Applied Chemistry*, 2025). This work establishes robust statistical approaches for proficiency testing involving nominal and ordinal data, extending capability into areas where traditional ANOVA-based methods are not applicable.

Recognition of excellence remains a core mechanism for advancing the field. Through the CITAC Best Papers 2024 awards, we highlighted work that sets clear benchmarks for the community. A dedicated seminar on June 17, 2025, showcased:

- J. Wollinger et al., who advanced metrological traceability through the independent certification of quantitative NMR (qNMR) internal standards; <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s00216-024-05671-5>
- G. D'Agostino et al., who established SI-traceable methods for extracting technology-critical elements from electronic waste, directly supporting circular economy objectives; <https://pubs.rsc.org/en/content/articlehtml/2024/ja/d4ja00235k>
- B. Giussani et al., who addressed the growing challenge of multivariate uncertainty in spectroscopic data modelling. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S016599362400534X>

Featured in the 2025 CITAC Newsletter, these contributions illustrate how rigorous

measurement science underpins both emerging technologies and data-intensive applications.

Developments within National Metrology Institutes further underscore the strategic relevance of our work. In February 2025, the European Commission's Joint Research Centre released EURM-060, the first certified reference material for microplastic particles in water. Developed in response to regulatory drivers, this material enables traceable measurements of mass concentration, particle number, and size distribution following reconstitution. CITAC actively encourages adoption of such reference materials to support harmonized approaches in emerging and policy-relevant measurement areas.

At the NMI community, the 30th meeting of the Consultative Committee for Amount of Substance (CCQM) at the BIPM (April 2025) advanced both key comparisons and the digital transformation of the measurement infrastructure. Notably, the committee endorsed the development of machine-readable reference material certificates aligned with FAIR data principles—an important step toward integrating metrology into digital and automated data ecosystems.

Capacity building remains essential to sustaining this momentum. In 2025, the International Summer School on Metrology in Varenna—organized by SIF in collaboration with INRiM, BIPM, PTB, and CEM—focused on climate science, quantum technologies, and digital transformation, reflecting the evolving scope of measurement science.

Standardization efforts have also progressed significantly. ISO/TC 344 completed ISO 33408:2025, *Guidance for the production of pure inorganic substance certified reference materials*. This document establishes much-needed best practices for producing high-purity inorganic and metallic reference materials used as primary standards, strengthening consistency and traceability across calibration hierarchies.

Looking ahead, CITAC's 2026 programme is deliberately focused on implementation and impact. We will co-host the EURACHEM/CITAC Workshop in Lisbon (May 10–12, 2026), centred on *Quality in Analytical Measurements: Uncertainty Evaluation and Results Interpretation*. The programme combines targeted training with technical exchange, equipping laboratories to apply new guidance and respond to evolving ISO accreditation requirements.

Under my chairmanship, CITAC has reinforced its role as a coordinating and driving force in chemical metrology. We have delivered practical guidance where it is most needed, strengthened alignment with key international bodies, and ensured that measurement science remains responsive to emerging regulatory and technological demands. Maintaining this trajectory will be essential. With continued engagement from our members and partners, CITAC is well positioned to provide sustained leadership in advancing comparable, SI-traceable chemical measurements worldwide.

ADDRESS OF THE VICE-CHAIR

THE DEMOCRATISATION OF THE EVALUATION OF THE MEASUREMENT UNCERTAINTY

Ricardo Bettencourt da Silva // University of Lisbon, Portugal

The publication of the first edition of the ISO/IEC 17025 standard in 1999¹ listed, for the first time, the evaluation of measurement uncertainty as a requirement, agreed internationally, for conducting competent quantitative tests. Although this document is especially relevant for accredited laboratories that must adhere to it, it also offers guidance for other test laboratories. Non-accredited laboratories can choose not to undergo external assessment for implementing the ISO/IEC 17025 standard, but their decision not to evaluate measurement uncertainty diverges from the international consensus on how this work should be carried out.

The chemical analysis field has struggled to meet the new accreditation requirement due to the complexity of some of its analyses, as measurement procedure performance can vary significantly depending on the characteristics of the analysed item, aside from the level of the determined quantity (i.e., the matrix). Therefore, analysts have developed pragmatic strategies for evaluating the measurement uncertainty that are

adequate on many occasions. The primary reference for developing such strategies is the ISO GUM, "Guide to the expression of uncertainty in measurement", first published in 1993². However, due to the difficulty of describing some measurements in chemistry as detailed mathematical relations of variables representing all effects affecting measurement performance, it was decided to use an alternative approach. The measurement performance data traditionally gathered during interlaboratory or intralaboratory validation of the measurement procedure are evaluated for the random and systematic effects expressed by the dispersion of observed results and deviations from reference values. The performance parameters are subsequently integrated into algorithms designed to quantify measurement uncertainty, occasionally accounting for additional uncertainty components not reflected in the data collected during validation. This evaluation strategy is briefly disseminated in the Eurachem/CITAC guide on Quantifying the Uncertainty in Analytical Measurements³ (QUAM),

³ Eurachem/CITAC Guide, Quantifying Uncertainty in Analytical Measurement (QUAM), 3rd Edition, Eurachem, 2012

¹ ISO/IEC 17025:1999, General requirements for the competence of testing and calibration laboratories, ISO, 1999.

² ISO/IEC Guide 98:1993, Guide to the expression of uncertainty in measurement (GUM), ISO, 1993

specifically in Examples A4 and A6 of the document.

However, since even pragmatic evaluation strategies has its own difficulties, because simplification is complex, more simplified evaluation approaches than the one described in the QUAM have been developed and disseminated. Although very popular, some further simplifications compromise the mathematical consistency of the uncertainty evaluation, affecting measurement accuracy and causing unnecessary overevaluation of the measurement uncertainty.

A new Eurachem/CITAC guide was published to provide analysts with detailed general guidance on a mathematically consistent way of using intralaboratory or in-house method validation data for the evaluation of the measurement uncertainty in line with the QUAM⁴. This guide should strengthen the link between the measurement uncertainty evaluation carried out in laboratories and the guidelines specified in the GUM² for all measurement types and in QUAM³ for measurement in chemistry.

Nevertheless, even if accredited laboratories are directed to adequate evaluations of the measurement uncertainty, we are still far from achieving the goal of widespread dissemination of good metrology practices in measurements in chemistry. We still need to persuade laboratories

outside the accreditation sphere that assessing measurement uncertainty is crucial for interpreting results and that these calculations are manageable for anyone willing to make a reasonable effort to understand the concept. Developing black box software without educating people about the underlying algorithm should not be the solution because individuals will not make decisions based on their results without understanding how decision-making is conducted.

It seems the solution to the identified problem is always the same: properly train people. We will arrive there because reality will compel analysts to conduct measurements properly.

Image generated by ChatGPT

⁴ Eurachem/CITAC Guide, Evaluation of measurement uncertainty from in-house

precision and recovery data, First Edition, Eurachem, 2026

ADDRESS OF THE VICE-CHAIR

THE NEW EURACHEM/CITAC GUIDE ON “EVALUATION OF MEASUREMENT UNCERTAINTY FROM IN-HOUSE PRECISION AND RECOVERY DATA”

Ricardo Bettencourt da Silva // University of Lisbon, Portugal

The Eurachem/CITAC Working Group on Measurement Uncertainty and Traceability (MUTWG) developed a new guide on how to use intralaboratory or in-house validation data of the measurement procedure for the evaluation of the measurement uncertainty. This document intends to complement existing guidance produced by Eurachem and other organisations on producing reliable evaluations of the uncertainty of measurements in chemistry.

The Eurachem Guide on “Quantifying Uncertainty in Analytical Measurement” (QUAM) presents the general principles on the evaluation of the measurement uncertainty, and, in example A4, exemplifies a specific use of in-house validation studies for the evaluation of the measurement uncertainty. The document does not detail guidance on how to use such type of information in another measurement or available data scenario.

Nordtest has published comprehensive guidance on how to use inter- and intralaboratory data supporting the validation of a measurement procedure for the evaluation of the measurement uncertainty. The documents of this organisation

follow a strategy different from that proposed in the QUAM regarding the handling of systematic effects. Instead of deciding on the need to correct results for poor recovery, results are not assessed for the need of recovery correction, and the measurement uncertainty is increased to compensate measured values for this option.

The new Eurachem/CITAC guide presents general guidance on the evaluation of the measurement uncertainty from in-house validation studies in line with the QUAM. This document also strictly follows the Guide on the expression of the measurement uncertainty (GUM) regarding the need to correct the result for recovery deviating significantly from 100%. The new guide ensures that the measured values are accurate and that the measurement uncertainty is not unnecessarily overestimated. These options are particularly relevant for cases where the tested item is assessed for conformity, even if the decision rule does not consider the measurement uncertainty.

The guide is presented as a tutorial that guides analysts in performing very simple calculations or more elaborated uncertainty evaluations when

the use of simplified algorithms produces results with inadequately high uncertainty, i.e. uncertainty larger than a target or maximum admissible uncertainty. This way, the analyst should only invest the energy and time strictly necessary to produce adequate measurement results. Detailed examples of how to perform measurement uncertainty evaluation are presented, evolving from the simplest cases to the more complex ones. An analyst willing to invest in studying the guide will benefit from getting the knowledge on how to produce more valuable analytical work, involving more accurate determinations with optimal uncertainty.

Regarding the content of the document, it should highlight the guidance on how to model the variation of measurement uncertainty with the measured value using information at one or more measured values, allowing for adapting the uncertainty evaluations to available data and narrow or wide analytical intervals. The guide also discusses how to handle results from the analysis

of reference materials, such as Certified Reference Materials and Spiked samples, where the various estimates of analyte recovery are not compatible. This section of the guide is particularly relevant considering the type of data routine laboratories frequently collect on measurement procedure validation and test quality control.

The MUTWG believes the new Eurachem/CITAC guide will contribute to advancing the way laboratories evaluate the uncertainty associated with chemical analysis, satisfying the increasingly demanding requirements of regulators and customers regarding the objectivity and quality of the interpretation of the analytical data.

Eurachem/CITAC Guide, Evaluation of measurement uncertainty from in-house precision and recovery data, First Edition, Eurachem, 2026.

Image generated by ChatGPT

MESSAGE FROM THE CITAC SECRETARY

FROM MEASUREMENT TO DECISION: MANAGING THE RISK OF FALSE CONFORMITY IN PHARMACEUTICAL ANALYSIS

Felipe Rebello Lourenço // University of São Paulo, Brazil

Analytical measurements performed in pharmaceutical laboratories are rarely an end in themselves. Their true purpose is to support decisions. These decisions determine whether a batch of medicine is released to the market, whether a manufacturing process remains under control, or whether corrective actions must be taken. Between the measurement result and the final regulatory or industrial decision lies a critical element that must not be overlooked: measurement uncertainty and the associated risk of false conformity decisions.

In pharmaceutical quality control, conformity assessment is generally based on comparing a measured value with predefined specification limits. However, a measurement result is not complete unless it is reported with its respective measurement uncertainty. When measurement uncertainty is ignored in decision-making, two undesirable outcomes may arise: 1) a non-conforming batch may be incorrectly accepted, representing a risk to patients; or 2) a conforming batch may be erroneously rejected, generating unnecessary economic loss and waste. These situations are commonly referred to as consumer's risk and producer's risk, respectively.

Managing these risks is not merely a statistical refinement of routine practice, but a matter directly linked to patient safety, regulatory compliance, and the sustainability of pharmaceutical operations.

Consider a simple univariate example involving the assay of a single active pharmaceutical ingredient (API) in tablets with a specification of 90.0 to 110.0% of the label claim. Suppose that a batch yields a result of 91.7%. At first glance, the product appears to be compliant. However, if the measurement uncertainty is considered, e.g., $91.7 \pm 2.5\%$ (expanded uncertainty with approximately a 95% confidence level), the interval associated with this result extends below the lower specification limit. In other words, even though the reported value lies within the acceptance range, there is a non-negligible probability that the true content is actually below 90.0%. If this probability is ignored and the decision is made solely on the basis of the measured value, the laboratory implicitly accepts a certain level of consumer's risk.

While the univariate case already illustrates the importance of using measurement uncertainty

information to support conformity decisions, pharmaceutical products are frequently more complex. Fixed-dose combination medicines containing two or more APIs are common in therapeutic areas such as cardiovascular diseases, infectious diseases, and oncology. In such products, conformity requires that each API simultaneously complies with its respective specification. Suppose a tablet containing API A and API B yields assay results of 108.8% and 109.2%, respectively, both formally within the specification interval of 90.0 to 110.0%. If the uncertainties of the two measurements are considered, the total risk of false acceptance corresponds to the joint probability that at least one parameter lies outside the specification limits. Even when the particular risk values are small, the total risk of false acceptance can be significantly increased when two independent criteria must be satisfied simultaneously.

The situation becomes even more complicated when the measurement results are correlated. In practice, the quantification of two APIs in the same dosage form can be correlated due to the product's characteristics (e.g. the way the medicine is manufactured) or due to shared analytical steps (e.g. shared sample preparation steps that affect both analytes). This correlation may increase or decrease the total risk of false acceptance.

This multivariate perspective demonstrates that conformity cannot always be reduced to a set of

isolated univariate decisions. Modern pharmaceutical quality control frequently involves multiple critical quality attributes, including assay, impurities, dissolution, degradation products, particulate matter, and other relevant parameters. When each test is evaluated independently without considering the total risk, the joint probability that at least one parameter lies outside its specification may be substantially higher than anticipated. A batch may formally pass all individual tests, yet still carry a non-negligible total risk of false acceptance.

Incorporating risk evaluation into pharmaceutical analysis does not imply excessive conservatism or unnecessary complexity. On the contrary, it promotes transparency and rationality. It enables laboratories and manufacturers to align decision rules with clearly defined protection levels, balancing patient safety with operational feasibility. It also enhances communication with regulators by making the assumptions and acceptable risk levels explicit rather than implicit.

In pharmaceutical analysis, measurement is only the beginning. The ultimate objective is a reliable decision that safeguards patients and ensures the integrity of therapeutic products. Whether dealing with a single API assay or with correlated measurements in a fixed-dose combination, managing the risk of false conformity requires moving beyond point estimates and embracing uncertainty-informed decision-making.

NEW MEMBERS

MESSAGE FROM CORPORATE MEMBER

VASILISA BARANOVSKAYA // AAC Analitica, Russia

AAC Analitica was created to combine the efforts of analytical laboratories in Russia in order to promote best practices in the field of analytical chemistry, testing, and diagnostics of substances and materials.

AAC Analitica promotes the exchange of experience and knowledge to improve the quality of laboratory work in Russia, develop international cooperation in the field of analytical control, metrology and standardization, and mutual recognition of test results.

For many years, Russia has been represented at CITAC. The Russian representative was academician Yuri Karpov, who for almost thirty years headed the AAC Analitica, advocating international cooperation in analytical chemistry and the metrology of chemical measurements. He was a key figure in promoting the development of common terminology and fundamental principles for laboratory quality. After academician Yuri Karpov left us, the Executive Committee of AAC

Analitica decided to continue with these important functions of international cooperation. With the support of CITAC members, AAC Analitica has become a corporate member since 2025.

AAC Analitica is an accreditation body for testing laboratories with a 35-year history. Since 2004, AAC Analitica has been a member of ILAC and APAC (former APLAC). Since October 2025 – a full member of Global Accreditation Cooperation Incorporated (Global ACI). Global ACI MRA Signatory for testing, reference material producers and PT providers.

AAC Analitica has been providing translation into Russian and popularization of CITAC documents in Russia for many years.

NEW MEMBERS

MESSAGE FROM INDIVIDUAL MEMBER

ELCIO CRUZ DE OLIVEIRA // Pontifical Catholic University of Rio de Janeiro, Brazil

Elcio Cruz de Oliveira is a chemist and metrologist with more than three decades of experience at the interface between analytical chemistry, metrology, and industrial applications. He holds a degree in Chemistry Education from the State University of Rio de Janeiro (UERJ), a master's degree in Metrology for Industrial Quality from PUC-Rio, and a PhD in Chemistry from the Federal University of Rio de Janeiro (UFRJ). His doctoral research focused on validation, uncertainty evaluation, data reconciliation, and conformity assessment applied to gas chromatography in industrial environments. He has also completed two postdoctoral appointments in Chemical Metrology, one at UFRJ and the most recent at the University of Lisbon.

Throughout his professional career, Dr. Oliveira has been closely associated with the Petrobras system, within the Brazilian oil and gas industry, where he has worked as a researcher for over 37 years. His work has focused on metrology applied to the measurement of quantity and quality in the logistics chain of petroleum, natural gas, biofuels, and derivatives. This includes custody transfer measurements, sampling uncertainty, data reconciliation, and the evaluation of risks associated with conformity assessment.

In parallel with his industrial activities, Dr. Oliveira has maintained a strong commitment to education and capacity building. He is currently a professor in the Graduate Program in Metrology

(PósMQI) at the Pontifical Catholic University of Rio de Janeiro (PUC-Rio), where he teaches courses related to measurement uncertainty, chemical metrology, experimental design, and data treatment. He also serves as an instructor and consultant for professional training programs organized by Brazilian institutions. He has supervised numerous MSc and PhD students and has been actively involved in interdisciplinary research projects spanning energy, environmental, pharmaceutical, and manufacturing sectors.

His research interests include chemical and physicochemical measurements, uncertainty arising from sampling, statistical modeling of analytical data, chemometrics, instrumentation, and the application of uncertainty and risk concepts in conformity assessment and regulatory decision-making. He has authored and co-authored numerous peer-reviewed papers, book chapters, technical reports, and national and international standards, and regularly serves as a reviewer and editorial board member for scientific journals in metrology and analytical chemistry.

As a relatively new member of CITAC, he sees his participation as an opportunity to strengthen international collaboration in chemical metrology, particularly in promoting good practices related to uncertainty evaluation, sampling, and decision rules in analytical

measurements. He is especially interested in contributing to discussions and initiatives that bridge academic research, industrial practice, and standardization, as well as supporting the dissemination of CITAC and Eurachem guidance documents within Latin America.

Dr. Oliveira looks forward to further engagement with the CITAC community and to contributing to ongoing efforts to advance traceability, reliability, and confidence in analytical chemistry worldwide.

NEW MEMBERS

MESSAGE FROM CORPORATE MEMBER & INDIVIDUAL NEW MEMBER

TONGXIANG REN // National Institute of Metrology, China

Dear friends,

It is a great honor for me to join CITAC. I am Dr. Tongxiang Ren from the National Institute of Metrology (NIM, China). NIM was established in 1955 and is affiliated with the State Administration for Market Regulation (SAMR). It is the nation's highest research facility of measurement science, a national statutory authority in the field of metrology, and a non-profit R&D institution. NIM is responsible for ensuring nationwide consistency and international equivalence of quantity values, maintaining the highest measurement capabilities in China, supporting the improvement of the quality of development of China, and facing the challenges of the new technological revolution.

Under NIM, there are 9 specialized divisions and 7 research centers. As one of the 9 divisions, Division of Chemical Metrology and Analytical Science mainly focuses on the development and maintain of national measurement standards, the research on reference materials and accurate measurement methods in the fields of organic chemistry, inorganic chemistry, food safety, clinical and medicine, and so on. Our missions are to establish a metrological traceability system for property value dissemination through research on national standards and primary standards system for chemical measurement, to engage in

international cooperation and international mutual recognition in order to establish national core measurement capabilities with international competitiveness, to carry out knowledge transfer both domestically and internationally.

Personally, since joining NIM in 2008, my research has primarily focused on isotope analysis. I have developed isotopic analysis methods using various mass spectrometry techniques, including multi-collector ionization coupled plasma mass spectrometer (MC-ICP-MS), thermal ionization mass spectrometer (TIMS), high resolution ionization coupled plasma mass spectrometer (HR-ICP-MS), and hyphenated techniques such as laser ablation (LA). My work involves absolute isotope abundance measurements. I have successfully carried out the atomic weight measurements of selenium and ytterbium, which were accepted as the best measurements by the International Union of Pure and Applied Chemistry-Commission on Isotopic Abundances and Atomic Weights (IUPAC CIAAW). Additionally, I have developed a number of isotopic reference materials and provided technical services externally.

In the future, NIM and I are very willing to work with CITAC members to jointly promote the improvement of international comparability in chemical measurement.

NEW MEMBERS

MESSAGE FROM CORPORATE MEMBER & INDIVIDUAL NEW MEMBER

SAMUEL TSZ-CHUN CHEUNG // Government Laboratory of the Hong Kong Special Administrative Region, China

It is an honour to introduce myself as the new Government Chemist of the Government Laboratory of the Hong Kong Special Administrative Region, China (GLHK). Having joined GLHK in 1998 and assumed this role in February 2026, I look forward to continuing our long-standing partnership with CITAC and contributing to the global advancement of chemical metrology.

Our Institution and Expertise

The GLHK is one of the oldest government departments in Hong Kong, with a history dating back to 1879. Today, we employ about 500 staff across two primary operational divisions:

- *Analytical and Advisory Services Division*: This division provides essential support for public health, food safety, environmental protection, as well as the protection of government revenue and consumer interests. Our expertise covers the testing for food composition and labelling, additives, contaminants, pesticides, and veterinary drug residues, as well as analysis of environmental samples, pharmaceuticals, and Chinese medicines.

- *Forensic Science Division*: This division delivers comprehensive forensic services to the criminal justice system in Hong Kong. Our expertise spans

physical sciences, DNA analysis for identification and individualisation of biological evidence, and toxicology. We also provide 24-hour crime scene attendance and examination services to law enforcement agencies, along with examinations of abused drugs, questioned documents, and chemical analysis related to offences against persons and property.

As the Designated Institute (DI) for metrology in chemistry in Hong Kong under the CIPM MRA, the GLHK is strongly committed to ensuring the international comparability and traceability of chemical measurements. We actively participate in international comparisons and serve as a proficiency testing (PT) provider to strengthen laboratory competence both locally and across the Asia-Pacific region.

Hopes for Involvement with CITAC

Since CITAC was established in 1993, it has served as an important platform for international collaboration and improving the international comparability of chemical measurement, a platform that the GLHK has long valued. As a staunch member of CITAC, my primary hope is to strengthen these ties further.

We look forward to sharing our experience in emerging areas of chemical analysis, including the

development of new testing methodologies, the provision of proficiency testing (PT) schemes and the development of reference materials for local and international testing communities.

Through active engagement in CITAC's initiatives, we aim to contribute to international guidelines

that address evolving challenges in metrology. We are excited to connect with fellow members and collaborate to promote traceability to the world.

LIAISON REPORTS

AFRIMETS REPORT

Angelique Botha // National Metrology Institute of South Africa (NMISA), South Africa / AFRIMETS TC-QM Chair

APMP REPORT

Tang Lin Teo // HSA, Singapore / APMP TCQM Chair

COOMET REPORT

Narine Oganyan // VNIIFTRI, Russia

EURAMET REPORT

Michela Segal // INRiM, Italy

SIM REPORT

Bryan Calderón Jiménez // LACOMET, Costa Rica / SIM MWG-08 Chair

Patricia Grinberg // NRC, Canada / SIM MWG-08 Vice-Chair

IMEKO REPORT

Michela Segal // INRiM, Italy / IMEKO TC8 Chair

REPORT FROM ISO/TC 334 REFERENCE MATERIALS

Angelique Botha // NMISA, South Africa, ISO/TC 334 Chair

LIAISON REPORTS

AFRIMETS ACTIVITIES

Angelique Botha // NMISA, South Africa / AFRIMETS TC-QM Chair

SUMMARY OF GENERAL ISSUES

AFRIMETS (the African regional metrology organisation) held its 18th General Assembly and related meetings from 21 to 25 July 2025 hosted by the Ghana Standards Authority (GSA) in Accra, Ghana. Most of the technical committees including the Technical Committee for Quality Systems (TC-QS) met before the General Assembly.

In terms of the election of executive officers, AFRIMETS noted with appreciation the availability of the current chairs and vice chairs for the next term. Dr Henry Rotich from the Kenya Bureau of Standards (KEBS) is currently the Chairperson of AFRIMETS, Mr Mathew Rangani from SIRDC in Zimbabwe is the Vice-Chair, Scientific together with Madame Souad Bouaziz from ANM in MAGMET. Mr Humphrey Nkobeni from ZMA in Zambia is the Vice-Chair for Legal metrology supported by Mr Abderazek Laouini also from ANM.

At the general assembly a decision was taken to make the two task groups, namely the Task Group on Medical Devices (TGMD) under the leadership of Dr Rasha Sayed Atia from NIS in Egypt and the Task Group on Digitalisation (TGD) under the leadership of Dr Ahmed Hussein also from NIS in Egypt, formal working groups of AFRIMETS.

The 19th General Assembly of AFRIMETS is proposed to be hosted by the Ethiopian Metrology Institute (EMI) in Addis Abeba in Ethiopia in August 2026.

CURRENT TECHNICAL COMMITTEE (TC) AND WORKING GROUP CHAIRS AND CONTACT DETAILS

The AFRIMETS structure includes working groups to mirror the international consultative committee working groups (CC-WGs) and are identified as TC-(parameter).

The contact details of the TC Chairs important to Chemistry and Biology are listed below:

Function	Name	Details
TC-QM Chair Vice-Chair (Bio analysis)	Dr Angelique Botha Ms Désirée Prevoo-Franszen	National Metrology Institute of South Africa (NMISA), Private Bag X34, Lynnwood Ridge, 0040, RSA Tel: +27 12 947 2705 e-mail: abotha@nmisa.org Tel: +27 12 947 2738 e-mail: dprevoo@nmisa.org
TC-Mass and Related Quantities	Mr Thomas Mautjana	National Metrology Institute of South Africa, Private Bag X34, Lynnwood Ridge, 0040, RSA Tel: +27 12 947 2880 e-mail: tmautjana@nmisa.org
TC-QS	Dr Noha Emad Khaled	National Institute for Standards (NIS), Tersa Street, El Haram, Giza, 12211 Egypt Tel: +(202)33862322 e-mail: nemadnis@yahoo.co.uk or nemadnis@netscape.net

AFRIMETS CMCs

As of 3 March 2026, there were a total of 823 AFRIMETS CMCs accepted in Appendix C of the KCDB

The CMCs originate from:	Zimbabwe (SIRDC) = 23
South Africa (NMISA) = 523 (131 CMCs in Chemistry and Biology)	Morocco (LPEE) = 20
Egypt (NIS) = 134 (22 CMCs in Chemistry)	Tanzania (TBS) = 18
Kenya (KEBS) = 43 (2 CMCs in Chemistry)	Zambia (ZMA) = 15
Tunisia (DEFNAT) = 25	Ethiopia (EMI) = 12
	Namibia (NSI) = 7
	Botswana (BOBS) = 3

DEVELOPMENT WORK IN CHEMISTRY AND BIOLOGY

In 2025, NIS in Egypt published 20 new Chemistry CMCs for their measurement capabilities for anions in a range of water matrices (seawater, contaminated water, drinking water, fresh water and ground water), certified calibration solutions for patulin (mycotoxins), platinum and palladium in advanced materials and heavy metals in rice. These CMCs will support their measurement services for the analysis of complex water matrices with ion chromatography and the reference materials they are producing for heavy metals and mycotoxins in a range of food matrices. Additionally, NIS is participating in the

supplementary comparison GULFMET.QM.S1: Benzoic and Sorbic acid in Ketchup.

KEBS in Kenya has taken action on the mandate from their government to develop and establish a capability for the production of reference materials in support of the economies of the East African Community (EAC). In February 2025, the metrology in chemistry group of KEBS received training in ISO 17034 and ISO 33405 for the competent production of reference materials. In the beginning of 2026, the testing groups of KEBS also received similar training including some training on the practical aspects of reference material preparation such as the sourcing, processing, subdivision and packaging of the reference materials.

Colleagues from the KEBS testing laboratories during the training session on ISO 17034 and ISO 33405 for the competent production of reference material

LNMc-INRAP in Tunisia submitted their first CMCs for certified calibration solutions for patulin and aflatoxins in 2025. In October 2025, the institute also received training on the new ISO 33400 series of standards for the production and use of reference materials to strengthen the quality

management system and enhance the knowledge of the technical team in terms of the latest guidance on the production of reference materials.

Metrologists from LNMc-INRAP during the training on the ISO 33400 series of standards training for reference material production supported by the PTB.

The calibration materials for the participants of the AFRIMETS supplementary comparison for pesticides in yellow plum (AFRIMETS.QM-S1) has now been received by the NMISA and the comparison samples are currently being prepared for shipment. The comparison will enable AFRIMETS NMIs, such as LNMc-INRAP in Tunisia, who has an advanced capability in this area, to claim new CMCs. Much interest has also been shown by developing NMIs from the SIM region, such as Columbia, Bolivia, and Argentina as well as from other NMIs active in the Organic Analysis Working Group (OAWG) of the CCQM.

AFRIMETS has also submitted a proposal to support Phase 3 of the Pan African Quality Infrastructure (PAQI) project *Harnessing quality infrastructure in the cassava value chain* with the organisation of a proficiency testing (PT) scheme for cassava. The PT scheme was conducted in 2024 for four (4) PT rounds. In Phase 3 of the project the PT scheme will be repeated with another four (4) PT rounds for the determination of the moisture and protein content in cassava; toxic and nutritional elements in cassava flour; pesticides in cassava and mycotoxins in cassava. Furthermore, AFRIMETS is collaborating with PTB on a project to strengthen food testing capacity for African commodity standards within the Africa Continental Free Trade Area (AfCFTA).

For any further information on the activities in AFRIMETS or the activities of the TC-QM for Chemistry, please contact:

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LIAISON REPORTS

APMP ACTIVITIES

Tang Lin Teo // HSA, Singapore / APMP TCQM Chair

ADVANCING CHEMICAL AND BIOLOGICAL METROLOGY IN THE ASIA-PACIFIC: HIGHLIGHTS FROM THE 25TH APMP TCQM MEETING ON 24 & 25 NOVEMBER 2025

The 25th meeting of the Asia Pacific Metrology Programme Technical Committee for Amount of Substance (APMP TCQM) brought together 59 delegates from 20 national metrology institutes (NMIs) and designated institutes across the Asia-Pacific region to review progress in chemical and biological metrology comparisons and activities,

as well as to discuss emerging priorities. The meeting, chaired by Dr Tang Lin Teo (Health Sciences Authority, Singapore), was held in Incheon, Republic of Korea. The meeting, held during the 8-day meetings of the 41st APMP General Assembly and Related Meetings also celebrated the 50th anniversary of the Korea Research Institute of Standards and Science (KRISS).

Delegates of 41st APMP General Assembly hosted by KRISS in Incheon, Republic of Korea

The TCQM serves as the regional coordination platform for metrology in chemistry and biology, ensuring measurement traceability to the International System of Units (SI) and supporting the recognition of calibration and measurement capabilities (CMCs) under the CIPM Mutual Recognition Arrangement. The meeting highlighted both the significant technical achievements across the region and the growing role of measurement science in addressing global challenges such as healthcare, food safety, climate change and emerging technologies.

PROGRESS IN CMC SUBMISSIONS AND REGIONAL CAPABILITIES

A major topic of discussion was the CMC review cycle XXVI, where APMP institutes submitted a substantial number of calibration and measurement capability claims for international recognition. In total, 234 CMCs were successfully submitted for international review, representing a major contribution from the Asia-Pacific region to the global metrology infrastructure.

The submissions covered several key service areas, including gases, water analysis and food measurements. These capabilities underpin a wide range of applications—from environmental monitoring and industrial emissions control to food safety testing and healthcare diagnostics.

The TCQM congratulated the National Metrology Institute, Malaysia (NMIM) for achieving its first pair of internationally recognised CMCs, marking an important milestone for developing metrology institutes in the region.

EXPANDING COMPARISONS AND COLLABORATIVE STUDIES

Interlaboratory comparisons remain a cornerstone of the CIPM MRA framework. APMP TCQM has organised a significant portfolio of studies to benchmark measurement capabilities and demonstrate equivalence across institutes.

To date, the committee has coordinated 15 key comparisons, 29 supplementary comparisons and 40 pilot studies, addressing measurement challenges across chemical and biological analysis.

Several new studies were approved during the meeting. These include comparisons on pesticide residues in water to be organised by the National Institute of Metrology, China, the Health Sciences Authority, Singapore and the Government Laboratory, Hong Kong, China, as well as adulterants in dietary supplements to be organised by Department of Chemistry, Malaysia and Health Science Authority, Singapore. Such studies are designed to support regulatory measurement needs, food safety assurance and environmental monitoring across the region.

In addition, proposals for new comparisons are being explored in emerging areas such as elements in cultivated meat, heavy metals in plant-based protein products and anions in water. These proposals reflect the rapid evolution of global food systems and environmental monitoring requirements.

BIO-METROLOGY AND PUBLIC HEALTH INITIATIVES

Bio-metrology is becoming an increasingly important focus for APMP TCQM. A workshop held alongside the meeting highlighted strong regional interest in areas such as food authenticity, microbiological safety and diagnostic measurement capabilities.

Participants identified several priority areas including DNA-based identification of food species, pathogen detection and quantification of genetically modified organisms (GMOs). These topics align closely with regulatory and public health needs across the Asia-Pacific region.

Another major initiative discussed was the APMP public health programme on clinical markers, which involves collaboration among 44 clinical laboratories and 10 in-vitro diagnostic manufacturers across six economies. The programme aims to improve measurement traceability for clinical biomarkers through value assignment activities conducted by several NMIs including HSA, KRIS, NIM, NMIJ and NIST.

These activities demonstrate how metrology in chemistry and biology can directly support healthcare systems and improve the reliability of diagnostic testing.

ADDRESSING GLOBAL CHALLENGES THROUGH METROLOGY

The meeting also reviewed developments from the Consultative Committee for Amount of Substance (CCQM), including its long-term strategic planning through 2034. Key focus areas include multi-omics measurement technologies, data digitalisation and new measurement challenges associated with gene delivery systems and advanced biomedical technologies.

Environmental measurement challenges were also highlighted. The CCQM Gas Analysis Working Group outlined strategic priorities related to greenhouse gases, hydrogen purity, biomethane and advanced spectroscopy for atmospheric monitoring. These activities support global climate monitoring efforts and emerging energy technologies.

Meanwhile, the APMP Climate Change and Clean Air Focus Group shared progress on initiatives to reduce measurement uncertainties in emissions monitoring and carbon flux observations, demonstrating the growing contribution of metrology to climate science.

CAPACITY BUILDING AND REGIONAL COLLABORATION

Supporting capability development across the region remains a central mission of APMP. Several training programmes and workshops were highlighted during the meeting, including a gas

analysis workshop hosted by NMIM, Malaysia that attracted over 80 participants from NMIs and industry.

Future training initiatives will include programmes on reference material production, gas metrology and water quality measurements. These activities are designed to strengthen measurement capabilities in developing economies and promote knowledge transfer across the metrology community.

LOOKING AHEAD: NOVEL FOOD MEASUREMENT AND EMERGING NEEDS

Looking forward, APMP TCQM is exploring measurement challenges associated with novel foods such as cultivated meat, insect-based protein and microalgae products. These rapidly evolving food technologies present new analytical requirements for contaminants, nutritional composition and biological safety.

Future TCQM workshops would engage regulators, industry and research organisations to better understand the measurement needs associated with these emerging food systems.

The next APMP TCQM meeting will take place in Wellington, New Zealand in November 2026, where further discussions will continue on how metrology can support innovation, public health and sustainable development in the Asia-Pacific region.

Delegates of 25th APMP TCQM Meeting hosted by KRISS in Incheon, Republic of Korea

LIAISON REPORTS

COOMET ACTIVITIES

Narine Oganyan // VNIIFTRI, Russia

COOMET (Organization for Cooperation of State Metrology Institutions of Central and Eastern Europe) is one of the regional metrology organizations worked with BIPM to promote world-wide uniformity in units of measurement, innovation, competitiveness, trade, consumer safety, sustainable development and ensure international recognition.

The last fifty years have been marked in most countries by a keen interest among scientists and politicians in the quality of life of population. Naturally, that metrology plays a key role in ensuring a high quality of our life, especially in areas where measurement underpins decision-making. So, today, metrology is the primary lever for ensuring mutual understanding and consistency in virtually all areas of society.

In this matter, special responsibility lies with the accuracy and reliability of chemical and biological measurements. Since, they are using everywhere: from the environment to food production, from pharmaceuticals to clinical diagnostics, from fresh water to wastewater treatment, and more. Thousands of chemical measurements daily help make decisions about food safety, health, and environmental protection. Based on these measurement results, decisions are made on

whether a product complies with established standards. And the risks of these decisions are directly dependent on the quality of the measurements and the comparability of the results obtained.

To establish mutual understanding between the metrology community and representatives of related disciplines, such ways as organizing joint seminars, conferences, round tables, etc. are important places.

Every year, the International Metrology Forum and Exhibition "Metrology Without Borders" are held in Moscow to mark World Metrology Day (<https://metrologicalexhibition.ru/>). The last event took place from May 19–21, 2025. The forum's business program alone brought together several hundred leading experts, government

representatives, international and regional metrology organizations, Russian industrial enterprises, and guests from neighboring and distant countries. One of the key events of the business program was the **All-Russian Conference of Participants of the State Service of Reference Materials (GSSO) of Russia**, where specialists discussed current challenges and development trends for reference materials in various economic sectors. New reference materials, developed by the state metrology institutes of Russia, were presented as a separate stand at the exhibition.

As part of the strategy to establish mutual understanding between related disciplines, once every two years (every odd-numbered year) the **International Scientific and Technical Conference "Metrology of Physicochemical Measurements" (MPM)** is held by VNIIFTRI (Russia) with the support of Rosstandart and with the participation of all Russian metrology institutes (<https://conference.vniiftri.ru/index.php/en/>).

From September 2 to 5, 2025, in the historic city of Yaroslavl (Russia), was organized the VIIth such conference (**MPM-2025**). There were metrologists from the Belarusian Metrology Institute (BelGIM) and Russian regional metrology centers, representatives of research institutes of the Russian Academy of Sciences (RAS): VNIIMP named after V.M. Gorbатов (for meat industry); NUST MISIS (Department of Crystallography); VGNKI (for Animal Feed and Drug Standardization and Quality); Bauman Moscow Technical University (MSTU) (Department of Biotechnology); Kurchatov Institute National Research Center (for

Nuclear Physics); Gormedtekhnika Institute (for medical instruments); Institute of Reference Materials (Russia); 'KRISTALL' Design Bureau; Vasilievsky Rudnik (ore mining); Cherkizovo Group (PJSC for meat products), and measuring instrument producers, among others. In total, more than 120 people took part in the conference.

With the same goal, the **International Scientific Conference "Reference Materials in Measurements and Technologies"** is organized by UNIIM-VNIIM (Russia) with participation of all Russian metrology institutes once every two years (every even-numbered year). The next (VIIth) such conference will be held from September 8 to 11, 2026, at the Kochubey Center, Pushkin, St. Petersburg, Russia (www.conference.gssso.ru).

One of the technical committees of COOMET, related to the Consultative Committee on the Amount of Substance: Metrology in Chemistry and Biology (CCQM), **TC 1.8 "Physical Chemistry"** (<https://coomet.info/structures/fizikohimiya>) held its annual meeting in a hybrid format in October 30-31, 2025, St. Petersburg, Russia. 22 National Metrology Institutes (NMIs) from 17 COOMET member countries represent at TC 1.8. **The TC Chairperson: Yuri Kustikov**. Representatives from Armenia, Belarus, Kazakhstan, China, Russia, Uzbekistan participated in the meeting. The meeting heard reports on the latest developments in metrology in each country over the past year, the work being carried out at the CCQM, the need to update the list of COOMET technical experts, the status of nine ongoing COOMET comparisons and pilot studies, and the update of five announced ones. It was also

proposed to organize three new comparisons in the areas of isotope analysis, gases, and GMO determination in corn.

According to country reports:

Belarus

BelGIM has expanded its measurement capabilities for calibrating X-ray fluorescence spectrometers with the acquisition of a set of reference materials of plastic composition (ROHS); its technical base has been expanded with the acquisition of an IR Fourier spectrometer and GSVS-META alcohol-air mixture generators; work is underway to expand capabilities in the field of measuring electrolytic conductivity in the range from 0.1 to 1.0 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ using water-non-aqueous solvent systems; to modernize the National Standard of the Unit of Mole Fraction of Atmospheric Environmentally Hazardous Components NE RB 18-10.

Kazakhstan

KazStandard has approved the State Standard of the Unit of Mass (Molar) Fraction and Mass (Molar) Concentration of Inorganic Components in Liquid and Solid Media Based on Spectrometry and Gravimetry Methods, KZ.01.01.00290-2025, designed to reproduce, store and transmit the size of the unit of mass concentration of inorganic compounds in liquid and solid media and the production of reference materials; a State Standard of Chloride Ion Solution Composition and a State Standard of Sulfate Ion Solution Composition have been developed; work has begun to expand the functionality of the State Standard of the Molar Fraction of Components in Gaseous Media by incorporating a new gas analytical complex based on the IR measurement

method, as well as gas chromatography for the analysis of sulfur-containing mixtures in gas mixtures.

Russia

A significant event of the year in Russia was the completion of a comprehensive state project aimed at developing new types of domestically produced reference materials. All Russian state metrology institutes participated in the project. Overall, 138 new types of reference materials and 43 new types of measures were developed between 2023 and 2025 (including 61 new types of reference materials and 21 new types of measures in 2025), which are in demand across various sectors of the country's economy.

As well as, in 2025:

VNIIM developed 34 new types of reference materials: CRMs for the composition of pesticides and organic acids; CRMs for the isotopic composition of calcium carbonate, polyethylene, and carbon monoxide; CRMs for the composition of gas mixtures of hydrogen sulfide in nitrogen, nitric oxide in nitrogen, nitrogen dioxide in nitrogen, and carbonyl sulfide in nitrogen in pressurized cylinders; CRMs for the composition of GM soybean DNA and GM corn DNA; CRMs for the specific electrical conductivity of liquids; CRMs for the composition of inorganic elements, ions, and substances to meet the needs of the national economy (food and light industry, petrochemistry, agro-industrial complex, environmental protection, etc.) in various fields of measurement.

UNIIM - VNIIM completed the improvement of 3 state primary standards of units of quantities in

the field of physicochemical measurements: GET 173 State Primary Standard of Units of Mass Fraction, Mass (Molar) Concentration of Water in Solid and Liquid Substances and Materials; GET 176 State Primary Standard of Units of Mass (Molar, Atomic) Fraction and Mass (Molar) Concentration of Components in Liquid and Solid Substances and Materials Based on Coulometry; GET 210 State Primary Standard of Units of Specific Adsorption of Gases, Specific Surface Area, Specific Pore Volume, Pore Size, Open Porosity and Gas Permeability Coefficient of Solid Substances and Materials; 118 new types of reference materials were developed in the field of quality control of food products, pharmaceuticals; solutions of nitric, phosphoric, sulfuric and hydrochloric acids; solutions of tellurium and scandium; magnetite composition; moisture content of grass seeds; specific surface area, pore size, specific absorption of nitrogen and argon, gas permeability of rocks; mass concentration of metals deposited on the filter from the air.

VNIIFTRI has developed reference materials of aqueous solutions: two mono-element metals (In and La) and one multi-element (10 components), four types of reference materials for electrolytic conductivity; as well as, the GET132 State Primary Standard of the Unit of Specific Electrical Conductivity of Liquids with range extension for the lower value from $1 \cdot 10^{-3}$ to $1 \cdot 10^{-7}$ S/m and the GET171 State Primary Standard of Ion Activity Indices in Aqueous Solutions have been improved.

In 2025, TC 1.8 completed the COOMET CMS review of the XXVIth cycle. The results were published in the BIPM KCDB. The COOMET CMCs were approved and published during this cycle:

VNIIM (including UNIIM-VNIIM):

- Gas analysis: 4 new and 62 modernized CMCs
- Inorganic analysis: 12 new CMCs
- Bioanalysis: 4 new CMCs
- Organic analysis: 10 new and 6 modernized CMCs

VNIIFTRI:

- Electrochemical analysis: 1 modernized CMC
- Inorganic analysis: 5 new CMCs

BelGIM:

- Gas analysis: 1 modernized CMC

Currently, the BIPM KCDB for metrology in chemistry and biology contains 555 VNIIM (including UNIIM-VNIIM) CMCs, 22 VNIIFTRI CMCs, 31 BelGIM CMCs, and 11 KazStandard CMCs. COOMET CMCs are distributed among measurement categories as follows: gas analysis – 357; organic solutions – 17; inorganic solutions – 32; metals and alloys – 14; sediments, soils, ores, and particulates – 21; high-purity chemicals – 75; biological fluids and materials – 11; food products – 23; water – 10; electrochemical analysis – 18; advanced materials – 31; other materials – 10.

In conjunction with the Conference MPM-2025, UNIIM-VNIIM (Russia) held a regular meeting of **COOMET Technical Committee 1.12 "Reference Materials"** (hereinafter referred to as **TC 1.12**), related to CCQM, on 4 September 2025 (Yaroslavl, Russia) in a hybrid format (the videoconference of the meeting was organized by the COOMET Secretariat (Uzbek National Institute of Metrology (UzNIM), Uzbekistan). The Chairperson of TC 1.12 is Egor Sobina (UNIIM-VNIIM, Russia). TC 1.12 joins representatives from 15 COOMET member countries: Armenia, Azerbaijan, Belarus, Bulgaria, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Cuba, Georgia, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Moldova, Russia, Slovakia, Tajikistan, Turkey and Uzbekistan (<https://coomet.info/structures/standartnye-obrazcy>).

The meeting was attended by 29 participants from seven COOMET member countries: Belarus,

Bosnia and Herzegovina, Kazakhstan, Russia, Tajikistan, Turkey, and Uzbekistan.

In 2025, TC 1.12 coordinated and organized the work of COOMET CRM specialists for 17 projects (coordinators were specialists from Russia, Belarus, Kazakhstan, and Uzbekistan), including four new projects to develop COOMET CRMs (coordinator: UNIIM-VNIIM, Russia):

- 949/RU/25 To Develop reference materials for the mass fraction of wet gluten in wheat grain;
- 950/RU/25 To Develop reference materials for steel composition;
- 951/RU/25 Comparative testing of certified characteristics of the reference materials for the composition and

properties of grade D coal (SO-46) - GSO 11299-2019;

- 952/RU/25 Comparative testing of certified characteristics of the reference materials for the composition and properties of grade Zh coal (SO-47) - GSO 11300-2019.

TC 1.12 also did on submitting 14 types of CRMs included in the BIPM KCDB for approval and registration as COOMET CRMs (COOMET standing project No. 858/RU-a/22). These CRMs were subsequently approved at the 37th COOMET Committee meeting (May 2025) and included in the Register of COOMET CRMs. The list of CRMs registered as COOMET CRMs in 2025 is given in the Table below.

List of CRMs registered as COOMET CRMs in 2025

№	Number at the COOMET Register / CRM number and CRM title at the National Registry
1.	CRM COOMET 0137-2025-RU/ GSO 9563-2010 CRM composition of dry milk (ASM-1)
2.	CRM COOMET 0138-2025-RU/ GSO 9734-2010 CRM composition of grain and its processed products
3.	CRM COOMET 0139-2025-RU/ GSO 10900-2017 CRM specific surface area of quartz sand (QSiO ₂ UNIIM CRM)
4.	CRM COOMET 0140-2025-RU/ GSO 11086-2018 CRM composition of dry milk products (set ACM-2 UNIIM CRM)
5.	CRM COOMET 0141-2025-R/ GSO 11087-2018 CRM composition of dry milk products (set ACM-2 UNIIM CRM)
6.	CRM COOMET 0142-2025-RU/ GSO 11127-2018 / GSO 11130-2018 CRM composition of dry grain-milk porridge for baby food (set KCM-1 UNIIM CRM)
7.	CRM COOMET 0143-2025-RU/ GSO 11131-2018 CRM of sorption properties of nanoporous silicon oxide (15-SiO ₂ UNIIM CRM)
8.	CRM COOMET 0144-2025-RU/ GSO 11144-2018 / GSO 11147-2018 CRM composition of dry cereal porridge for baby food (set KC-1 UNIIM CRM)
9.	CRM COOMET 0145-2025-RU/ GSO 11154-2018 CRM Sorption properties of nanoporous silicon oxide (2,2-SiO ₂ UNIIM CRM)
10.	CRM COOMET 0146-2025-RU/ GSO 11155-2018 CRM Sorption properties of nanoporous silicon oxide (6-SiO ₂ CO UNIIM CRM)
11.	CRM COOMET 0147-2025-RU/ GSO 11268-2019 / GSO 11270-2019 CRM composition of compound feed (set KK-1 CO UNIIM CRM)
12.	CRM COOMET 0148-2025-RU/ GSO 11271-2019 CRM composition of egg powder (ЯП-1 UNIIM CRM)
13.	CRM COOMET 0149-2025-RU/ GSO 11713-2021 CRM composition of potassium iodate (KIO ₃ UNIIM CRM)
14.	CRM COOMET 0150-2025-RU/ GSO 11858-2021 CRM composition of the beryllium solution (set Be)

In addition, the TC examined the submitted documentation of one type of Russian CRM (CRM for the composition of tin solutions (set of Sn UNIIM CRM) - GSO 12281-2023), included in the BIPM KCDB. Based on positive expert opinions, this type of CRM with the TC Resolution was submitted for approval by the COOMET Committee.

The Ratio of COOMET CRMs among COOMET member countries as of 1 March 2026 is shown in figure below.

Ratio of the 150 types COOMET RMs among COOMET member countries

Another area of TC 1.12's activity is related to the coordination and organization of cooperation on projects for development and revision of COOMET documents related to reference materials. Accordingly, the COOMET CRM Document Revision Plan has been updated for harmonization with the corresponding ISO documents. Particularly, the revising of two documents is currently underway in the following projects:

- 863/BY/22 Update of COOMET document D3/2008 "Memorandum of Understanding on the Development and Use of Reference Materials for the Composition and Properties of Substances and Materials within COOMET" (Coordinator: BelGIM, Belarus);
- 819/RU-a/20 "Coordination and implementation of the Plan for the revision of COOMET documents on CRMs for harmonization with international ISO documents" - Revision of COOMET recommendation R/RM/16:2007 "COOMET recommendations for the inclusion of reference materials in Appendix C of the CIPM MRA" (Coordinator: UzNIM, Uzbekistan).

Following the meeting of COOMET TC 1.12, a meeting of the Working Group on Reference Materials of the Composition and Properties of Substances and Materials of the Scientific and Technical Commission on Metrology (WG RM NTKMetr) of the Interstate Council for Standardization, Metrology, and Certification (EASC), which currently includes 10 CIS member states, was held. In 2025, based on the results of the WG RM NTKMetr's work, 97 types of national CRMs (96 types of Russian CRMs and 1 type of Belarus CRM) were recognized as interstate reference materials (MSOs). MSOs can be freely used in various fields, including in the legal metrology, of the states, acceded to the recognition, without additional testing, or research, or approval of the type of reference material in accordance with the national legislation. The following countries took part in the recognition of 97 types of national GCOs as MSOs: the Republic of Azerbaijan, the Republic of Armenia, the Republic of Belarus, the Republic of Kazakhstan, the Kyrgyz Republic, the Russian Federation, the Republic of Tajikistan, and the Republic of Uzbekistan.

The dynamics of recognition of national CRMs as interstates (MSOs) is presented in Figure below. Information about the ratio of MSOs among the countries as of 01.03.2026.

Ratio of MSOs among the countries as of 01.03.2026

Dynamics of approval of national CRMs as MSOs

In 2025, as part of the activities of the WG RM NTKMetr, UNIIM-VNIIM (Russia) developed the Program for the Creation and Application of Interstate Reference Materials for the Composition and Properties of Substances and Materials for 2026–2030 (hereinafter referred to as the Program), which was presented and adopted at the 68th meeting of the EASC (December 11, 2025).

The Program was prepared to coordinate the activities of national bodies in implementing intergovernmental agreements and EASC decisions related to metrological support for the uniformity of measurements in the state - members of the Agreement. All states of the Agreement will equally benefit from the results of this Program.

The development and application of the MSOs will facilitate the development of a number of CIS Agreements, will contribute to the elimination of technical barriers and the high-quality execution of trade and settlement transactions, will improve the metrological level and quality of measurements in priority areas of cooperation between the CIS countries in the extraction and processing of hydrocarbon raw materials, in energy conservation testing, in the nano industry, in the testing of agricultural products, environmental objects (soil, air, drinking and

waste water), strategically important objects (rocks and materials, industrial raw materials), in the field of healthcare and clinical diagnostics, etc.

In addition, another important event related to the review of CMCs was held in 2025 as part of the activities of COOMET.

To assess and support the quality of the measurement capabilities of COOMET member countries' metrology institutes, a training Seminar for potential COOMET auditors was held at VNIIM (St. Petersburg, Russia) on July 7-8, 2025. Representatives of metrology institutes from Belarus, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Russia, Tajikistan, and Uzbekistan participated in the event. The seminar served as a platform for discussing key issues related to the international acceptance of calibration and measurement capabilities, assessing quality management systems, and interchange experience within the framework of the CIPM MRA.

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LIAISON REPORTS

EURAMET ACTIVITIES

Michela Segà // INRiM, Italy

EURAMET is the Regional Metrology Organization (RMO) of Europe. It coordinates the cooperation of National Metrology Institutes (NMIs) and Designated Institutes (DIs) in Europe in different fields of metrology, such as traceability of measurements to the SI units, international recognition of national measurement standards and related Calibration and Measurement Capabilities (CMCs), research projects. Through the knowledge transfer and cooperation among its members, EURAMET facilitates the development of the national metrology infrastructures.

EURAMET is currently chaired by Dolores Del Campo (CEM, Spain); the two Vice-Chairpersons are Annette Röttger (PTB) who succeeded to Miruna Dobre (SMD, Belgium) for the General Assembly (GA) and Maguelonne Chambon (LNE, France) for the *European Metrology Programme for Innovation and Research (EMPIR)* and the European Partnership on Metrology related matters. EURAMET has at present 38 full members, plus the European Commission which has the role of associate with observer at the GA and 82 associates (DIs). Its white paper "Metrology for a stronger Europe – A European Metrology Agenda for the next decade" (<https://www.euramet.org/about-euramet/metrology-for-a-stronger-europe-white-paper>) outlines the EURAMET vision of a European Metrology Agenda for the decade 2030 to 2040. It calls for a coordinated European metrology response building on the needs arising

from the transition of the energy supply, protection of the environment, a strong, sovereign, and competitive European industry, digital transformation, circular economy, developments of the health system, and resilience of European infrastructures. The 19th EURAMET GA took place as a hybrid meeting from 2nd to 6th June 2025, in Berlin, UK, hosted by PTB, the German NMI. During the GA, a special event was devoted to the celebration of the 150th anniversary of the Metre Convention; two workshops on the hot topics of "Digitalisation" and "Making a strong case for the value of metrology" were also held. The 20th EURAMET GA will take place in the week from 1st to 5th June 2026 in Tbilisi (Georgia), and will be hosted by GEOSTM, the Georgian National Metrology Institute, which obtained the status of full membership in 2024.

European Partnerships are a key implementation tool of the European Commission's Horizon Europe, an ambitious research and innovation programme, running from 2021 to 2027. Among these, the European Partnership on Metrology (Metrology Partnership, EPM) aims at bringing together the measurement science community and stakeholders to deliver on global challenges including health and digital transformation, support the European Green Deal, and underpin innovation and competitiveness in industry through collaborative research. The EPM is co-funded by the Member States and the European Union with an expected budget of around 690

million euro. The expected impact of the EPM is manifold, as it aims to support a wide range of policies, commerce and advancement of key European challenges. It is articulated in seven call cycles between 2021 to 2027, covering topics such as Green Deal, Health, Digital Transformation, Fundamental Metrology, Integrated European Metrology, Industry needs, Pre-normative and Knowledge transfer and capacity building measures. The Partnership builds on the progress achieved under the previous European Metrology Research Programmes, and aims to break new ground by contributing to the development of self-sustaining, coordinated metrology infrastructures, with the capacity to continue joint research and innovation after 2030.

In 2025 a call within the EPM framework was launched, via the usual two stage process, on the following major topics, addressing specific challenges: Integrated European Metrology, Health, Normative (Regulation), metrology support for research potential. Stage 1, opened in January, aimed at offering stakeholders from any country the opportunity to influence the projects undertaken by the European Community by identifying potential research topics. The highest priority topics received at Stage 1 provided the basis for Stage 2 which opened on 24th June 2025. In November 2025 the review conference was held, after which the call ranked list was published, thus establishing the projects to be financed within the call. In 2026 another call within the EPM framework was launched on the following major topics: Industry, Fundamental metrology, Normative, Research potential. Stage 1 opened on 8th January 2026 and closed on 16th February. The highest priority topics received at Stage 1 will provide the basis for Stage 2 which will open on 24th June 2026. Major information on the calls can be found at <https://www.metpart.eu/>.

The European Metrology Networks (EMNs) represents one of the most important initiatives undertaken by EURAMET for the promotion of cooperation conceived in a broader scope towards better partnership, communication, and harmonization. EMNs are collaborative structures which go beyond joint research to increase the coordination of measurement

science across Europe, addressing scientific and societal challenges, infrastructure and services in response to European and global metrology needs. Currently there are twelve EMNs: Advanced Manufacturing, Clean Energy, Climate and Ocean Observation, Energy Gases, Laboratory Medicine, Mathematics and Statistics, Pollution Monitoring, Quantum Technologies, Radiation Protection, Safe and Sustainable Food, Smart Electricity Grids and Smart Specialisation in Northern Europe. Each EMN, by providing a single point of contact, aims at underpinning regulation and standardization by establishing a comprehensive and longer-term infrastructure, promoting best practice and disseminating knowledge in its respective fields. Further EMNs are under consideration to address additional challenges in response to the current international scenario. More information on EMNs can be found at <https://www.euramet.org/european-metrology-networks/>.

Technical collaboration in EURAMET is organized within ten Technical Committees (TCs), focusing on specific areas which represent the forum for scientific and technical cooperation in the respective fields. In addition, two Committees deal with the overall topics Quality and Interdisciplinary Metrology (<https://www.euramet.org/technical-committees>). The TCs are responsible for the execution of the activities required by EURAMET as RMO for the fulfilment of the Mutual Recognition Arrangement of the International Committee of Weights and Measures (CIPM-MRA). The types of technical cooperation carried out within the TCs are: cooperation in research, comparison of measurement standards, metrological traceability, and consultation on facilities.

One of the ten TCs is devoted to Metrology in Chemistry (Technical Committee for Metrology in Chemistry, TC-MC), which is concerned with primary methods and reference materials for chemical measurements and research in metrology to support different sectors in the amount of substance fields (<https://www.euramet.org/technical-committees/tc-mc>).

NEWS FROM EURAMET TECHNICAL COMMITTEE IN METROLOGY IN CHEMISTRY (TC-MC)

TC-MC is chaired by Teemu Näykki (SYKE, FI), who served for two terms. In 2026 the election of the new TC-MC chairperson was carried out: the elected chair, Florbela Dias (IPQ, PT) will formally take office in June 2026, during the next EURAMET GA. 33 EURAMET member countries are represented in TC-MC plus the European Commission. BIPM has the status of observers.

The technical activities are carried out within the four technical Sub-committees dealing with gas analysis (SC-GA), inorganic analysis (SC-IA), electrochemical analysis (SC-EA), bio and organic analysis (SC-BOA). The convenors of the subcommittees are: Janneke van Wjik (VSL, NL) for SC-GA, Rainer Stosch (PTB, DE) for SC-IA, Gavin O'Connor (PTB, DE), and Anton Petrenko (SE Ukrmetrteststandard) for SC-EA who took over the responsibility from Matilda Roziková (CMI, CZ). In addition, a strategy working group, chaired by the TC-Chair, is also active on the following tasks: advice to TC-Chair and subcommittee convenors, strategic planning of comparisons, support actions, coordination, organization of workshops.

The TC-MC members are actively participating in the European Programmes on Metrology, being involved in all the targeted programmes; in addition, they cooperate within various EMN, among which Climate and Ocean Observation, Energy Gases, Mathematics and Statistics, Pollution Monitoring, Safe and Sustainable Food, Traceability in Laboratory Medicine, thus indicating the cross-disciplinary nature of the TC itself.

TC-MC meeting in 2025

The annual meeting of the TC-MC was held in Borås, Sweden, hosted by RISE from 4th to 6th February 2025. The Strategy WG had an online meeting on 29th January.

The four technical subcommittees reconvened, as usual, ahead of the annual TC-MC plenary meeting on 4th February 2025. A review of new CMC claims as well as the obligatory re-review of a range of existing claims were carried out. Running and new projects and comparisons in the

framework of EURAMET, EMPIR, EMP and also proposals for the upcoming EMP call were discussed in detail in all sub-committees.

The plenary meeting took place on 5th and 6th February 2025. An update on EURAMET and BIPM/CIPM activities, including a focus on progress on recommendations and new initiatives since the BIPM-WMO Workshop on Metrology for Climate action and the outcomes of the 1st CIPM STG-CENV stakeholder meeting was given. Some highlights on CCQM strategy and activities within its main working groups were also given. The activities carried out within the liaison organization Eurachem were presented, including a proposal of a MoU between EURAMET and Eurachem. The convenors of the subcommittees gave an overview of the activities of each subcommittee and of the main outcomes of the meetings carried out in the previous day. The convener of SC-BOA gave some information on the proposal of a summer school on Bioanalysis, scheduled for 2026 and organized together with the university of Braunschweig. A section of the meeting was devoted to EMNs dealing with topics related to the amount of substance field. An overview was given on the EMN for Climate and Ocean Observation (coordinated by NPL), EMN for Energy Gases (coordinated by VSL), EMN for Laboratory Medicine (coordinated by LNE), EMN for Pollution Monitoring (coordinated by LNE) and EMN for Safe and Sustainable Food (coordinated by INRiM). On 5th February a specific workshop in preparation for the 2025 EMP call was held, addressing all the different targeted programmes.

TC-MC meeting in 2026

The annual meeting of the TC-MC was held in Ljubljana, Slovenia, hosted by MIRS and NIB, from 2nd to 5th February 2026. The Strategy WG had an online meeting on 22nd January.

The four technical subcommittees reconvened, as usual, ahead of the annual TC-MC plenary meeting on 3rd February 2026. A review of new CMC claims as well as the obligatory re-review of a range of existing claims were carried out. Running and new projects and comparisons in the framework of EURAMET and EMP and also project proposals for the upcoming EMP call were discussed in detail in all sub-committees.

The plenary meeting took place on 4th and 5th February 2026. An update on EURAMET and BIPM/CIPM activities, including a focus on the BIPM technical support to CCQM strategy, was

given. Some highlights on CCQM strategy and activities within its main working groups were also given. The activities carried out within the liaison organization Eurachem were presented, including the MoU between EURAMET and Eurachem, signed in 2025. The conveners of the subcommittees gave an overview of the activities of each subcommittee and of the main outcomes of the meetings carried out in the previous day. The convener of SC-BOA gave some information on the summer school on Bioanalysis, scheduled in 2026 and organized together with the university of Braunschweig. A section of the meeting was devoted to EMNs dealing with topics related to the amount of substance field. An overview was given on the EMN for Climate and Ocean Observation (coordinated by METAS), EMN for Energy Gases (coordinated by VSL), EMN for Laboratory Medicine (coordinated by LNE), EMN for Pollution Monitoring (coordinated by LNE) and EMN for Safe and Sustainable Food (coordinated by INRiM). On 4th February a specific workshop in preparation for the 2026 EMP call was held, addressing all the different targeted programmes, and representing an effective forum to exchange ideas and promote the constitution of consortia.

The next TC-MC meeting will be held from 2nd to 4th February 2027 in Sarajevo, Bosnia-Herzegovina, hosted by IMBiH.

LIAISON REPORTS

SIM ACTIVITIES

Bryan Calderón Jiménez // LACOMET, Costa Rica / SIM MWG-08 Chair

Patricia Grinberg // NRC, Canada / SIM MWG-08 Vice Chair

Bryan Calderón
Jiménez

Patricia Grinberg

Abstract

This report highlights recent strategic actions of the Interamerican Metrology System (SIM). Specifically, the Metrology Working Group in Chemistry & Biology (MWG-08) to strengthen chemical metrology across the region. Key initiatives include the launch of a new web page as a communication platform, a regional diagnostic of capabilities, gaps and needs, and the development of data-driven and preventive tools to improve CMC review processes.

1. Strengthening Communication and Information: The New MWG-08 Website

A major milestone for MWG-08 has been the launch of its new website, now hosted within the SIM portal ([MWG-08 website](#))

Home News About SIM Official Documents Projects

Chemistry and Biology

MWG-8 CHEMICAL METROLOGY

BRIEF DESCRIPTION

The **Chemical Metrology Working Group (MWG-08)** of the **Inter-American Metrology System (SIM)** supports SIM and its member National Metrology Institutes (NMIs) and Designated Institutes (DIs) in fulfilling the requirements of the **CIPM Mutual Recognition Arrangement (CIPM MRA)** in the fields of chemical and biological metrology.

From environmental monitoring to healthcare, including food quality and food safety, metrology in chemistry and biology provides essential tools to ensure the traceability and reliability of measurement results. It also plays a vital role in supporting fundamental research, including nanotechnology, biosciences, biotechnology, fair trade, and innovation.

MWG-8 focuses on primary methods and reference materials for chemical measurements. It also conducts collaborative research to meet the needs of customers and stakeholders.

The group coordinates cooperation among NMIs and DIs across the Americas, aiming to:

- Provide national measurement standards in chemical and biological measurements.
- Ensure traceability of measurement results to the **International System of Units (SI)** where applicable.
- Achieve international recognition of national measurement standards and **Calibration and Measurement Capabilities (CMCs)**.

MAIN TASKS AND AREAS OF INTEREST

- Organizing regional key and supplementary comparisons, as well as pilot studies, in chemistry and biology metrology, and linking these activities to the **CCQM** of the **BIPM** and to other Regional Metrology Organizations (RMOs);
- Facilitating cooperation in preparing, reviewing (including intra- and inter-RMO review processes), publishing, and maintaining **CMC** claims of member NMIs and DIs in the **KCDB**;
- Disseminating knowledge and promoting technical cooperation through meetings, workshops, awareness seminars, and training opportunities at various NMIs and DIs;
- Promoting harmonization among members through sustainable networking.

New MWG-08 website. (MWG-08 website)The platform introduces a clearer and more structured architecture, enabling direct access to core components such as organizational structure, technical areas, strategic activities, and key documentation.

SIM Comparison Report (Chemistry & Biology)

The following table presents the status of comparisons organized within SIM by the various working groups in the fields of chemistry and biology from 2009 to present.

Working group	Pilot Lab	Published Year	Identifier	Measurement Capability	Status	Number participants
OAWG	CENAM-INMETRO	2023	SIM.QM-S17	Ethanol in Water	KCDB (Published on)	13
IAWG	NRC	2012	SIM.QM-S2	Trace elements in water	KCDB (Published on)	11
	NRC-CENAM	2018	SIM.QM-S7	Trace metals in drinking water	KCDB (Published on)	16
	NRC	2021	SIM.QM-S10	Trace Elements in Skim Milk Powder	KCDB (Published on)	12
	LATU	Pending	SIM.QM-S11& P25	Trace of As, Cd, P and Na in Mate	KCDB (Published on)	16
	NRC	2023	SIM.QM-S12	Elements in Natural Water	KCDB (Published on)	21
	CENAM-INMETRO	Pending	SIM.QM-S13	Elements in Cu Concentrate & Ore	Draft B & Final Report (presented to IAWG)	11
	INMETRO	Pending	SIM.QM-S16	Metals in Water	Running	22
GAWG	NRC	Pending	SIM.QM-S1&P27	Cadmium and lead in cacao powder	Final Report	18
	NIST-CENAM	2009	SIM.QM-S1	Binary gas mixtures	KCDB (Published on)	2
	NIST-INMETRO	2025	SIM.QM-S3	Methane in air	KCDB (Published on)	2
	NIST-INMETRO	2025	SIM.QM-S4	Nitric oxide in nitrogen.	KCDB (Published on)	2
	CENAM-KRISS	2023	SIM.QM-S5	Natural Gas	KCDB (Published on)	7
	INMETRO	2023	SIM.QM-S6	Automotive Emissions	KCDB (Published on)	5
	INMETRO	2023	SIM.QM-S9	Biogas	KCDB (Published on)	4
	CENAM	Pending	SIM.QM-S14	Carbon Dioxide in Nitrogen	Draft A (under discussion)	4
	CENAM	Pending	SIM.QM-S15	Methane in Air	Draft B (under discussion)	4
	NAWG	CENAM	Pending	SIM.QM.Pilot study SARS-CoV-2 DNA Copy number quantification	Draft A (under discussion)	4

*CICQM Working groups: Electrochemical Analysis (EAWG), Gas Analysis (GAWG), Inorganic Analysis (IAWG), Isotope Ratios (IRWG), Nitric Acid Analysis (NAWG), Organic Analysis (OAWG), Protein Analysis (PAWG), Surface Analysis (SAWG), Cell Analysis (CAWG).

Information on regional comparisons available through the new website. (MWG-08 website)

Beyond improved accessibility, the website enhances transparency and visibility at both regional and international levels. Strategically, it serves as a central hub for harmonization, knowledge transfer, and capacity building, particularly for emerging areas. The integration of WordPress and Google Drive ensures efficient information management, traceability, and continuity across leadership periods, addressing previously identified gaps in knowledge transfer.

2. Building a Baseline: Diagnosis of Metrological Needs and Gaps in the SIM Region

Between November 2025 and March 2026, MWG-08 conducted a regional diagnostic to establish a baseline of capabilities and needs in chemical metrology.

Results confirm a strong foundation in the region, with 88.9% of institutions reporting published CMCs. However, development remains uneven. While inorganic, organic, gas, and food analysis are well established, emerging fields such as bioanalysis, clinical biomarkers, and nanometrology show limited and fragmented growth.

A key finding is the misalignment between existing capabilities and emerging demands;

particularly in areas linked to climate change, health, and sustainability. This highlights the need for more integrated and cross-cutting strategies.

Structural barriers were also identified, including funding limitations, infrastructure gaps, and shortages of specialized personnel. Additionally, the need to strengthen competencies in uncertainty estimation, statistical analysis, and interpretation of intercomparison results emerged as a critical educational challenge.

Priority areas were identified including: gas analysis (H₂, refinery gases, GHGs), stable isotope measurements, emerging contaminants (Hg, microplastics, nanomaterials) and food and environmental metrology.

Further details about the diagnostic questionnaire and its report can be found in the next links ([MWG-08 Diagnostic Questionnaire Report](#)) ([MWG-08 Diagnostic Questionnaire](#)).

3. Lessons Learned: Analysis of KCDB Comments for the SIM Case

A data-driven tool was developed to analyze KCDB comments using R (RScript available here: <http://rpubs.com/BRY/1418741>).

1.6. Indicate current areas of chemical metrology specialization in your NMI (select all that apply):

Degree of specialization of participating institutes (MWG-08 Diagnostic Questionnaire Report).

Distribution of comments during the XXVI cycle (2025).

After filtering administrative comments, clear technical trends emerge:

- 70% related to measurement uncertainty
- 15% to metrological traceability

- 8% to comparison evidence

These results confirm that uncertainty remains the dominant evaluation criterion and a systemic challenge across the region.

Distribution of comments across RMOs.

The analysis also reveals strong alignment among RMOs, reinforcing the robustness of the CIPM MRA framework while simultaneously increasing the level of technical demand on developing NMIs.

Key strategic implications that must be addressed in the short term include the implementation of pre-submission technical checklists ([MWG-08 CMCs Review Perspective](#)), strengthening documentation (focused in evidence, methods, and CMC scope), harmonization of uncertainty criteria and strategic planning of intercomparisons, including future-oriented studies.

4. Building and Maintaining Capabilities: Analysis of CMCs – Cycle XXVII (2026)

An executive analysis of Cycle XXVII CMCs was conducted using newly developed analytical code: <http://rpubs.com/BRY/1418324>

A) Fields, B) Matrices, C) Analytes, D) Techniques.

The results show predominance of inorganic metrology, growth in electrochemistry field and reduced participation in organic chemistry for this cycle. Common matrices include water, food, and gas mixtures, while analytes are dominated by toxic and major elements. As expected, spectroscopic techniques (ICP-OES, ICP-MS) prevail.

This confirms a mature and demand-driven inorganic metrology landscape, but it also highlights the need to promote other fields of chemical metrology such as organic chemistry, bio-metrology, among others, consistent with the regional diagnostic. The analysis further underscores the critical role of comparisons as drivers of capability development.

5. New Practical Guide for CMC Review: A Preventive Approach

A revised practical guide for CMC review has been developed with the aim of providing writers, reviewers and experts involved in the publication of CMCs at the regional level with greater clarity on the process ([MWG-08 Practical Guide](#)).

Chemical Metrology CMC Review Process:
Reviewer's perspective
Rev 3.0

Scope

This document aims to provide a practical and quick perspective on the key aspects that must be assessed and evaluated during the review or claim process of CMCs in the field of chemistry.

Purpose

This document provides readers with key points to expedite the CMC processes, as well as guide CMC claimers towards the aspects that their CMCs would be evaluated. In addition, this document exemplifies the main mistakes that could be made or avoided when CMCs are submitted to KCDB 2.0. Therefore, we encourage you to provide a quick but detailed reading of these aspects that can help you in this important task.

The NMI can send CMCs to be reviewed in each cycle in case of: new CMC, modified CMC or part of a scheduled re-review category. For information regarding the CMC process, please refer to documents listed in the associated documentation section- through the BIPM internet page.

Associated Documentation

- [CCQM-GAWG guidance document for purity analysis and CMC claims](#)
- [CIPM MRA G-13](#): Calibration and measurement capabilities in the context of the CIPM MRA. Guidelines for their review, acceptance and maintenance

MWG-08 Practical Guide.

Specifically, this new guide introduces a reviewer-oriented perspective, addressing:

- Key technical criteria
- Frequent errors

- Documentation requirements
- Alignment with KCDB 2.0

It also incorporates a structured checklist and emphasizes critical aspects such as uncertainty consistency, traceability, and validation through comparisons.

This marks a shift from a corrective to a preventive approach, directly targeting root causes identified in previous analyses. Its implementation is expected to reduce technical comments, improve submission quality, and enhance review efficiency.

6. Advancing Regional Comparisons and Strategic Projects

Progress in the organization of regional comparisons has continued to strengthen metrological capabilities across SIM. A key milestone was the 2024 publication of the SIM.QM-12 comparison (pilot: NRC), which supported the declaration of new CMCs in the current cycle. This comparison addressed toxic elements (Cd and Pb) in cocoa, a matrix of high regional relevance, demonstrating the alignment of metrological activities with regional priorities.

In parallel, several intercomparisons are currently underway. These include SIM.QM-S16 (pilot: INMETRO), focused on elemental measurements in drinking water, and SIM.QM-S14 and SIM.QM-S15, both targeting the development of capabilities in greenhouse gases (GHG). Together, these efforts reflect a strategic shift toward addressing environmental and sustainability-related measurement challenges.

More information on MWG-08 intercomparisons is available here: ([MWG-08 Intercomparisons](#))

At the project level, significant progress has also been achieved through the implementation of the REMERSIM initiative, aimed at establishing a regional Metrology Network for Renewable Energy. This project focuses on strengthening metrological infrastructure through proficiency testing, method validation, and the development and dissemination of reference materials

relevant to clean energy applications, particularly low-carbon hydrogen.

As part of this effort, SIM has supported the acquisition of primary reference materials (PRMs) from NPL (UK). These materials will be used by INMETRO (Brazil) to produce secondary PRMs for distribution among participating NMIs, enabling them to evaluate their measurement systems and advance their capabilities in reference material production.

REMERSIM project (GH2).

Overall, these initiatives illustrate a coherent regional strategy that integrates comparisons, infrastructure development, and emerging application areas, reinforcing SIM's role in supporting energy transition and environmental sustainability.

General Conclusions and Recommendations

The initiatives developed by MWG-08 represent significant progress in strengthening chemical metrology in the SIM region. Key achievements include improved communication, data-driven diagnostics, systematic analysis of CMC processes, and the development of practical tools.

However, important challenges remain, particularly in emerging areas such as bioanalysis, climate-related measurements, and nanometrology, as well as in funding and infrastructure.

To address these challenges, it is recommended to strengthen regional training programs, also it is necessary promote comparisons in emerging fields, expand the use of digital analytical tools, consolidate regional collaboration mechanisms and finally continue developing practical and strategic guidance documents.

References

1. [MWG-08 Website](#)
2. [MWG-08 Diagnostic Questionnaire](#)
3. [MWG-08 Diagnostic Report](#)
4. [MWG-08 KCDB Comments \(RScript\)](#)
5. [MWG-08 KCDB Comments Report](#)
6. [MWG-08 CMCs Analysis Report](#)
7. [MWG-08 CMCs Analysis Code](#)
8. [MWG-08 Practical Guide](#)

LIAISON REPORTS

IMEKO ACTIVITIES

Michela Segà // INRiM, Italy, IMEKO TC8 Chair

IMEKO, the International Measurement Confederation, founded in 1958, is a non-governmental federation of 41 Member Organizations individually concerned with the advancement of measurement technology. It has a consultative status with UNESCO and UNIDO and is one of the five Sister Federations within FIACC - Five International Associations Co-ordinating Committee. Its fundamental objectives are the promotion of international interchange of scientific and technical information in the field of measurement and instrumentation and the enhancement of international co-operation among scientists and engineers from research and industry.

Prof. Paolo Carbone (Italy) is the President and Prof. Frank Härtig (Germany), as past President, is currently the Advisory President and Chair of the Advisory Board. Dr. Barbara Goldstein (USA) is the President Elect and Chair of the Technical Board and Prof. Pasquale Daponte (Italy) is the vice President in charge of the XXV IMEKO World Congress. IMEKO Secretariat is located in Budapest (Hungary). The technical work of IMEKO is articulated within 26 Technical Committees (TCs) which are formed by experts in a specific field with common aims. The TCs organize symposia, conferences, workshops, seminars on specific topics at regular intervals; in addition, they publish proceedings of events, text-books, glossaries, studies. More information about IMEKO and its structure can be found on the IMEKO website (www.imeko.org).

The IMEKO 2025 General Council Sessions took place on 30th-31st August in Prague (Czechia) at the Institute of Theoretical and Applied Mechanics, ITAM. The first day opened with a workshop for the TCs, led by the President Elect, where the participants gave insights into the activities of TCs and shared ideas related to the organisation of conferences. The Kosovo Metrology Agency (KMA) was welcomed as a new Member Organisation. 21 new members within IMEKO TCs and 7 new TC officers were approved. Some statistics on the continuously increasing success of the IMEKO Journals were presented. The support for the establishment of the new TC26 Metrology for Cultural Heritage was expressed. Reports from the Information Officer and from the Secretary General were also given. IMEKO Partners APMP, EURAMET, SIM, EUROLAB and the Confederation of European Environmental Engineering Societies - CEEES participated in the General Council Sessions and presented the latest developments and activities in their organizations and future plans.

The year 2025 was characterized by numerous IMEKO events organized by the TCs, among which:

- IMEKO TC2 PhotoMet 2025 - International Symposium on Modern Photonic Metrology, PhotoMet 2025 - Shaping the Future of Photonic Metrology, Modena, Italy, 1-3 September 2025 (<https://www.photomet.org/>)
- TC14 ISMQC 2025 - The 13th International Symposium on Measurement and Quality Control - Quality and Accuracy in the Age of

Data Driven Manufacturing, Cluj-Napoca, Romania, 2-5 September 2025 (<https://ismqc.utcluj.ro/>)

- IMEKO TC6 M4Dconf2025 - International Conference on Metrology and Digital Transformation Benevento, Italy, 3-5 September 2025 (<https://www.m4dconf.org/>)
- IMEKO TC8, TC11 and TC24 Joint conference, Torino, Italy, 14-17 September 2025 (<https://www.imekotorino2025.org/>)
- IMEKO TC7 and TC13 "Test and Measurement" Conference 2025, Pretoria, South Africa, 15-17 September 2025 (<https://www.nla.org.za/tm-2025-conference-workshop/>)
- TC23 8th IMEKOFOODS Conference, Food Safety and Metrology for a Sustainable Future, Ljubljana, Slovenia, 22-24 September 2025 (<https://conferences.imeko.org/event/12/>)
- IMEKO TC17 ISMCR 2025 - 26th International Symposium on Measurement and Control in Robotics, Sambreville, Belgium, 7-8 October 2025 (<https://ismcr.org/2025-ismcr/>)
- IMEKO TC26 MetroArcheo Conference 2025 - Metrology for Archaeology and Cultural Heritage, Bergamo, Italy, 15-17 October 2025 (<https://www.metroarcheo.com/>)
- IMEKO TC12 TEMPMEKO – ISHM 2025, XVth Symposium on Temperature and Thermal Measurements in Industry and Science and VIth International Symposium on Humidity and Moisture,

Reims, France, 20 - 24 October 2025 (<https://tempmeko-ishm2025.com/>)

- IMEKO TC4 Workshop at a Special Session at XVI Semetro, 1-4 December 2025, Centro Cultural e de Exposicoes Ruth Cardoso in Maceio - Alagoas, Brazil, 1-4 December 2025 (<https://metrologia2025.org.br/>).

TCs can select best contributions to IMEKO events to be published, as enhanced versions of the corresponding papers, in *Measurement*, the official journal of IMEKO, after the events. Additional contributions to IMEKO events can be also published in the IMEKO Online Journal ACTA IMEKO, which published its four issues in 2025 (<https://acta.imeko.org/index.php/acta-imeko>). In addition, three more specific open access journals are also available, in line with the rapid growth of studies on the relevant topics: *Measurement: Sensors*, *Measurement: Food*, and *Measurement: Energy*. A new Journal *Measurement: Digitalization* has been launched and there are plans for an additional one on Quantum in 2026. Periodic newsletters are prepared by IMEKO Secretariat and can be accessed through IMEKO webpage

(<https://www.imeko.org/index.php/newsletter>). The preparation for the XXV IMEKO World Congress is ongoing. It will take place at the Palacongressi di Rimini (Italy) from 30th August to 3rd September 2027. The call for submission of proposal for Special Sessions is open and will close on 31st August 2026. The submission of extended abstract will open on 15th October 2026. More information and updates can be found on the dedicated website (<https://imeko2027.org/>).

LIAISON REPORTS

ISO/TC 334 - REFERENCE MATERIALS

Angelique Botha // NMISA, South Africa, ISO/TC 334 Chair

6th annual meeting of ISO/TC 334 in June 2025

The 6th annual meeting of ISO/TC 334 was held as a hybrid meeting in conjunction with the 16th *International Symposium for Biological and Environmental Reference Materials* (BERM-16) in Halifax, Nova Scotia, Canada, during the first week of June 2025 (<https://berm.agendae.ca/>). The number of participants who joined the meeting were 20 'in-person' and 52 'on-line' with representatives from 18 member bodies. There are also three liaisons managed at ISO level (JCGM/WG1 responsible for the *Guide to the Expression of Uncertainty in Measurement* (GUM), JCGM/WG2 responsible for the *International Vocabulary for Metrology* (VIM) and JCTLM responsible for measurement traceability in laboratory medicine). The meeting included dedicated sessions where liaison representatives from other ISO technical committees and external organisations were invited to update the committee on items in their programme of work or other issues that could be of interest to ISO/TC 334.

A specific general business activity of ISO/TC 334 during 2025 included working with ISO on the Demarch project to update strategic business plans (SBPs). ISO/TC 334 is one of the committees that successfully updated its SBP, and the SBP is live on the ISO website with the updated look and feel – link @ www.iso.org/bp.

Program of work of ISO/TC 334

The program of work of ISO/TC 334 have now been updated based on the decisions taken at the sixth meeting and are listed below. The program includes the transformation of the existing ISO/REMCO Guides as well as the new work items of the committee that have been transformed into international standards. ISO/TC 334 currently has one remaining project in hand in the development of the ISO 33400 series of standards. i.e. ISO 33400 on the terms and definitions related to reference materials.

During the sixth meeting of the committee, based on the results of the committee internal ballots (CIBs) on the relevance of the technical reports (TRs) and further deliberations in the meeting, it was resolved that;

- ISO/TR 79 – '*Reference materials – Examples of reference materials for qualitative properties*', a revision is underway as an ISO approved work item (ISO/AWI TR79). The working group will review the current examples in the TR to align them with the new guidance available in ISO 33406. However, the focus will be to add more examples of qualitative RMs that are currently being produced in accordance with ISO 33406.
- ISO/TR 10989 – '*Reference materials – Guidance on, and keywords used for, RM categorization*' will be withdrawn.

- ISO/TR 11773 – ‘Global distribution of reference materials’ will be withdrawn.
- ISO/TR 16476 – ‘Reference materials – Establishing and expressing metrological traceability of quantity values assigned to reference materials’ will be withdrawn.
- ISO 33403 (previously ISO Guide 33) – ‘Reference materials – Requirements and recommendations for use’
- ISO 33405 (previously ISO Guide 35) – ‘Reference materials – Approaches for characterization and assessment of homogeneity and stability’

Figure below depicts the relationships between the different documents previously developed and currently being developed by ISO/TC 334.

- ISO/FDIS 33400 (previously ISO Guide 30) – ‘Reference materials – Selected terms and definitions’
- ISO 33401 (previously ISO Guide 31) – ‘Reference materials – Contents of certificates, labels and accompanying documentation’
- ISO/TR 33402 (previously ISO Guide 80) – ‘Good practice in reference materials preparation’
- ISO 33406 (previously WD/ISO Guide 85) – ‘Approaches for the production of reference materials with qualitative properties’
- ISO 33407 (previously WD/ISO Guide 86) – ‘Guidance for the production of pure organic substance certified reference materials’
- ISO 33408 (previously AWI/ISO Guide 87) – ‘Guidance for the production of pure inorganic substance certified reference materials’

Schematic diagram of the ISO 33400 series of standards for the transformation of the ISO/REMCO Guides 30 to 35 to international standards as well as the other projects of ISO/TC 334.

Update on the progress with the transformation of the ISO/REMCO Guides into the ISO 33400 series of standards

Five of the new standards of the ISO 33400 series were published in 2024; the sixth anticipated transition (ISO Guide 80) was published in 2025 as ISO/TR 33402 – ‘*Good practice in reference material preparation*’ as well as the new standard ISO 33408 – ‘*Guidance for the production of pure inorganic substance certified reference materials*’. ISO 33400 for the terms and definitions related to reference materials has been submitted to ISO Central Secretariat (CS) for the final draft international standard (FDIS) stage of balloting. Publication of the standard is anticipated to take place around the middle of 2026.

Within the working group responsible for the drafting of ISO 33400 there have been some discussions about including new terms in the standard, such as operationally defined measurand. There is also strong support in the working group to refer to a certified reference material as a reference material with one or more certified property value and to specify the characteristics of a certified value, such as the requirement for a value with an associated uncertainty and established metrological traceability in the definition of certified value.

ISO 33406 for the production of qualitative reference materials has been received very well by the chemical and biological testing communities. In September 2024, a very successful joint workshop between EURACHEM and CITAC was held to introduce the standard to the community ([https://www.eurachem.org/index.php/events/](https://www.eurachem.org/index.php/events/workshops/521-wks-qrm2024)

[workshops/521-wks-qrm2024](https://www.eurachem.org/index.php/events/workshops/521-wks-qrm2024)). The program of the workshop included a brief introduction to the standard. Several producers of qualitative reference materials were invited to present how the guidance from ISO 33406 was incorporated in the production of their qualitative reference materials. The working group has started with a new work item to update ISO/TR 79 ‘*Reference materials – Examples of reference materials for qualitative properties*’. The plan is to include more examples of how to produce qualitative reference materials in the technical report and to align the examples with the guidance developed in ISO 33406.

ISO/TC 334 has also established a new ad hoc group under the convenorship of Dr Takeshi Saito from AIST in Japan to investigate the issue of metrological traceability of certified values of CRMs. The aim of the group is to advance the state of our knowledge on how to establish metrological traceability for certified values. Additionally, the group will also investigate the status quo in terms of statements of metrological traceability of certified values on RM certificates. The objective of this work is to develop internationally harmonized guidance on how to draft statements of metrological traceability for certified values. It is hoped that this work will help producers to know what the correct information is to put on reference material (RM) certificates so that users will be able to select appropriate CRMs for their measurement challenge.

The 7th annual meeting of ISO/TC 334 will be a virtual meeting from 22 to 24 June 2026.

CITAC BEST PAPER AWARD 2025

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Introduction

The 12th meeting of the International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA) on the Development of Stable Isotope Reference Materials was held in Vienna from 22 to 26 January 2024. Since the first meeting in 1967, these meetings have guided the IAEA reference material (RM) program and the broader stable isotope community. A parallel session addressed formal definitions and practical realization (i.e., how the scale definition is practically realized) of isotope delta scales for light elements.

Participants included representatives from IAEA, National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST), United States Geological Survey (USGS), International Bureau of Weights and Measures (BIPM), the International Union of Pure and Applied Chemistry (IUPAC), other leading metrology institutes and other experts from academia.

The article summarizes consensus outcomes, namely, the agreed template for isotope delta scale definition, the consensus about the carbon isotope delta scale, the definition of VPDB and VPDB-LSVEC scales and the definition of the main oxygen isotope delta scales (VSMOW-SLAP and VPDB/VPDB-CO₂). This summary is based on the original paper published in *Rapid Communication in Mass Spectrometry*¹ and cites the published definitions and examples.

Isotope Delta Scale Definition and Realization

Isotope delta values are not traceable to SI (the International System of Units) but they are traceable to reference materials that define the isotope delta scales.²

An isotope delta scale is defined by taking a fixed numerical consensus delta value (without uncertainty) of a material, selected by international agreement. This definition determines one point in the delta scale (often but not always the zero point). Some isotope delta scales are defined by two distinct points.

During the meeting, a standardized format for isotope delta scale definitions was proposed and agreed upon. The format follows the template used for defining SI units in the SI Brochure. It consists of a concise defining statement for the scale, accompanied by explanatory notes. The defining text includes the name of the scale, the isotope name, the symbol for the isotope delta, the fixed numerical isotope-delta values for RM or all RMs that define the scale, and the identity of the zero point. Examples of isotope scale definitions following this format are provided below for carbon and oxygen.

Any modification to the defining text, particularly the adoption or revision of fixed points, would establish a new scale and therefore require a new name to distinguish it from earlier scales. In

contrast, explanatory notes that provide guidance related to a scale definition may be revised without creating a new scale.

Realizing the isotope delta scale means putting the scale definition into practice by using as calibrants one or more reference materials (RMs) with assigned values and associated uncertainty, which are consistent with the definition of the scale. As indicated in the traceability exception for delta value isotope ratio measurement,² approved by the International Committee for Weights and Measures (CIPM) in March 2015 these materials are listed and published by the International Union of Pure and Applied Chemistry, IUPAC (currently by Brand et al.³).

Carbon Isotope Delta Scales

Historically, the carbon scale was defined using NBS 19 calcite with an assigned stable $\delta(^{13}\text{C})$ of +1.95 ‰.^{4,5} In 2006, LSVEC lithium carbonate was introduced as a second scale-defining point, defining the VPDB-LSVEC scale.^{6,7}

In 2015, LSVEC was found to be unstable for carbon isotope analysis due to CO_2 absorption from the air. Although still suitable for lithium isotope measurements, it was no longer recommended for carbon isotope analysis.⁸

This led to intense discussions since 2016 within several communities and networks, such as the Isotope Ratio Working Group (IRWG) of the Consultative Committee for the Amount of

Substance (CCQM) of CIPM; the 2016, 2021 and 2024 Technical Meetings on IAEA stable isotope ratio reference materials; and the IUPAC Commission on Isotopic Abundances and Atomic Weights (CIAAW) amongst others.⁹ The debate concerned which carbon isotope scale to adopt (VPDB or VPDB-LSVEC)⁹ and whether they represent truly distinct scales or different realizations of a single scale.

After eight years of intense discussion, during the meeting the participants reached a consensus in acknowledging the existence and use of two carbon isotope delta scales with the following names:

VPDB

VPDB-LSVEC

The participants agreed on the definitions of the two scales reported in the original paper¹ and summarized below. Figures 1 and 2 offer a schematic representation of the two carbon isotope delta scales.

VPDB carbon isotope delta scale definition

The VPDB scale for the carbon-13 isotope delta value, expressed as $\delta(^{13}\text{C})$, is defined by taking the fixed numerical value of +0.00195 for the $\delta(^{13}\text{C})$ of the NBS 19 Reference Material, when expressed relative to VPDB.

Figure 1: Schematic representation of the VPDB carbon isotope delta scale, with delta values, multiplied by 1000, expressed in permille (‰):.

VPDB-LSVEC carbon isotope delta scale definition

The VPDB-LSVEC scale for the carbon-13 isotope delta value, expressed as $\delta(^{13}\text{C})$, is defined by taking the fixed numerical value of +0.00195 for $\delta(^{13}\text{C})$ of the

NBS 19 Reference Material, and -0.0466 for the $\delta(^{13}\text{C})$ of the LSVEC Reference Material, when expressed relative to VPDB.

Figure 2: Schematic representation of the VPDB-LSVEC carbon isotope delta scale, with delta values, multiplied by 1000, expressed in permille (‰).

Notes to the carbon isotope delta scales:

The quantity isotope delta is dimensionless and has the unit one. It is common practice to express numerical values of isotope delta, when multiplied by 1000, using the symbol permille (‰): for example, the consensus $\delta(^{13}\text{C})$ value of NBS 19 is +1.95 ‰.

VPDB stands for Vienna Pee Dee belemnite and LSVEC is a lithium carbonate originally prepared by H.J. Svec¹⁰ for use as a stable lithium isotope reference material.

VPDB is a virtual reference material, it does not and has not existed in material form. Its $\delta(^{13}\text{C})$ value is exactly 0 on the VPDB scale.

Carbonate reference materials, such as NBS 19 which is quarantined,⁸ or IAEA-603¹¹ that can be used instead of NBS 19, provide a means for analysts to realize the VPDB and VPDB-LSVEC scale in practice. In the case of VPDB-LSVEC scale, due to reported instability of the material, LSVEC, is no longer recommended for realizing the VPDB-LSVEC scale. Other reference materials whose values have been determined relative to the VPDB-LSVEC scale continue to provide accurate representations of this scale.

Carbon isotope delta values reported on the VPDB and VPDB-LSVEC scales can differ. Differences between delta values reported on the VPDB and VPDB-LSVEC scales range from +0.14 ‰ to +0.30 ‰^{12,13} for materials with carbon isotope delta values around -45 ‰ and are negligible (below current analytical combined uncertainty) at carbon isotope delta values close to zero. Conversion models between the two scales can be established and used but will introduce uncertainty.¹²

Oxygen Isotope Delta Scales

Two main oxygen isotope delta scales are currently available:

The VSMOW-SLAP scale, defined by water RMs and typically used for measurement of $\delta(^{18}\text{O})$ and

$\delta(^2\text{H})$ of water or hydrogen- or oxygen-bearing materials.

The VPDB scale, defined by a carbonate RM and used for measurement of $\delta(^{13}\text{C})$ and $\delta(^{18}\text{O})$ of carbonates and carbon dioxide.

Because IRMS measurements are performed on CO_2 rather than water or carbonate directly, the two scales can be coupled through the comparison of the $\delta(^{18}\text{O})$ in CO_2 that is equilibrated with VSMOW (VSMOW- CO_2), and $\delta(^{18}\text{O})$ in CO_2 produced from a RM whose $\delta(^{18}\text{O})$ value has been determined on the VPDB scale by reaction with concentrated phosphoric acid at 25 °C (VPDB- CO_2). The difference in the numerical values of $\delta(^{18}\text{O})$ between these two carbon dioxide gases is small (the latest published value is -0.28 ‰)¹⁴ with the $\delta(^{18}\text{O})$ of VSMOW- CO_2 being slightly negative with respect to VPDB- CO_2 .

Because preparing CO_2 from calcite using oversaturated phosphoric acid is a potentially error-prone process, it was confirmed, consistent with the agreement reached more than three decades ago at the 1993 CIAAW meeting in Lisbon, that the VSMOW-SLAP scale should serve as the primary oxygen isotope delta scale and the VPDB/VPDB- CO_2 scale should be defined in terms of the VSMOW-SLAP scale.

Here below the summary of agreed definitions for VSMOW-SLAP and VPDB/VPDB- CO_2 oxygen isotope delta scales and their schematic representations in Figures 3 and 4.

VSMOW-SLAP oxygen isotope delta scale definition

The VSMOW-SLAP scale for oxygen-18 isotope delta value, expressed as $\delta(^{18}\text{O})$, is defined by taking the fixed numerical value of 0 for $\delta(^{18}\text{O})$ value of the VSMOW Reference Material and -- 0.0555 for the $\delta(^{18}\text{O})$ value of the SLAP Reference Material, when expressed relative to VSMOW.

Figure 3: Schematic representation of the VSMOW-SLAP oxygen isotope delta scale, with delta values, multiplied by 1000, expressed in permille (‰).

VPDB and VPDB-CO₂ oxygen isotope delta scale definitions

The VPDB scale for oxygen-18 isotope delta value, expressed as $\delta(^{18}\text{O})$, is defined by taking the fixed numerical value of -0.0022 for $\delta(^{18}\text{O})$ of the NBS 19 Reference Material, when expressed relative to VPDB.

The VPDB-CO₂ scale for oxygen-18 isotope delta value, expressed as $\delta(^{18}\text{O})$, is defined by taking the fixed numerical value of -0.0022 for $\delta(^{18}\text{O})$ of the CO₂ gas liberated from the NBS 19 Reference Material in reactions with oversaturated phosphoric acid at 25 °C, when expressed relative to VPDB-CO₂.

Figure 4: Schematic representation of the VPDB oxygen isotope delta scale, with delta values, multiplied by 1000, expressed in permille (‰).

Notes to the oxygen isotope delta scales:

The quantity isotope delta is dimensionless and has the unit one. It is common practice to express numerical values of isotope delta, when multiplied by 1000, using the symbol permille (‰).

VSMOW stands for Vienna Standard Mean Ocean Water, and SLAP standards for Standard Light Antarctic Precipitation.

Whilst limited amounts of the original VSMOW and SLAP scale-defining reference materials may still be available, to enable continuous wide

distribution of RMs for VSMOW-SLAP scale realization, the scale-maintaining reference materials VSMOW2 and SLAP2 are available. VSMOW2 and SLAP2 have $\delta(^{18}\text{O})$ values identical to VSMOW and SLAP, respectively, but with an uncertainty with respect to VSMOW and SLAP.

The $\delta(^{18}\text{O})$ value of SLAP with respect to VSMOW has been based on consensus¹⁵ and might well not be the exact value.¹⁶ Therefore, oxygen isotope delta values reported on the VSMOW-SLAP scale and those reported using VSMOW only might differ.

VPDB stands for Vienna Pee Dee belemnite. It is a virtual material; it does not and has not existed in material form. The $\delta(^{18}\text{O})$ value of VPDB is 0 on the VPDB scale. The most recent $\delta(^{18}\text{O})$ value of VPDB is taken to be 0.03092 on the VSMOW-SLAP scale (assumed exact).^{3,17}

All $\delta(^{18}\text{O})$ values on the VPDB and VPDB-CO₂ scales can be converted to $\delta(^{18}\text{O})$ values on the VSMOW-SLAP scale or relative to VSMOW-SLAP-CO₂ scale using the oxygen isotopic fractionation factors reported in the

literature^{14,17} and the established difference between VSMOW-CO₂ and VPDB-CO₂. When appropriate, users should state the conversion equation they use in their publications.

Recommendations

IUPAC recommends the use of at least two reference materials to minimize common sources of instrument measurement bias.¹⁸

Reference material producers should demonstrate that their assigned values and uncertainties on such reference materials are consistent with the scale definition and with values and uncertainties for other reference materials intended for the same purpose. Measurement uncertainty assessments must include the uncertainties of reference materials, with additional components possibly required for materials on the VPDB-LSVEC scale.

When reporting their measurement results, users should follow the minimum requirements established by IUPAC.¹⁹

Users must clearly state:

Which RMs were used for data normalisation

The isotope delta values and relevant uncertainty of used reference materials

On which scale (VPDB or VPDB-LSVEC for $\delta(^{13}\text{C})$, VSMOW-SLAP or VPDB/VPDB-CO₂ for $\delta(^{18}\text{O})$) they are reporting delta values

Endorsement

During the September 2025 meeting in Tokyo, Japan, of the Commission on Isotopic Abundances and Atomic Weights (CIAAW) of the International Union of Pure and Applied Chemistry (IUPAC), the CIAAW endorsed all isotope delta scale definitions above and agreed to publish the current and all future updates and corrections to Camin et al. (2025) on its website (www.ciaaw.org).

Additional Topics of discussion

Additional topics of discussion during the meetings were the following:

Definition of the nitrogen and sulfur isotope delta scale which currently miss consensus

Development of greenhouse gas RMs (CO₂, CH₄, N₂O)

SI-traceable absolute isotope ratio measurements

Interlaboratory comparisons (e.g. CCQM exercises)

Production of new organic and inorganic RMs

Statistical tools for RM value assignment and uncertainty estimation

Centralized storage of RM characterization data

Large interlaboratory variability in $\delta(^2\text{H})$ of non-exchangeable hydrogen

Need for standardized procedures for carbonate-phosphoric acid reactions

Draft guidance for $\delta(^{13}\text{C})$ and $\delta(^{18}\text{O})$ calculation by Dual Inlet – IRMS (DI-IRMS)

Conclusion

The panel of experts at the IAEA meeting (Vienna, 22-26 January, 2024) acknowledged the existence and defined two carbon isotope delta scales: VPDB and VPDB-LSVEC. For oxygen, the VSMOW-SLAP scale was defined as the primary scale, with the

VPDB or VPDB-CO₂ scale defined relative to VSMOW-SLAP.

The panel emphasized that users must clearly state the reference materials used for normalization, the assigned values of those materials and the scale used. Producers of reference materials should ensure clear traceability of assigned isotope values and associated uncertainties. Embracing these recommendations will enhance transparency, reliability, and reproducibility in the reporting of stable isotope analysis and will thereby minimize hidden biases.

The panel also agreed on the need for further research to improve interlaboratory consistency in the isotopic analysis of non-exchangeable hydrogen in bulk organic materials and of oxygen in carbonates measured via the phosphoric acid reaction. Additionally, the development of new reference materials, particularly for greenhouse gases, as well as harmonized protocols for data calculation, normalization, and the assignment of values and uncertainties to reference materials, was recommended.

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CITAC BEST PAPER AWARD 2025

Activity Coefficients of HCl in Solutions Related to 'Tris' Buffers in Artificial Seawater. III. Tris Buffer + NaCl + H₂O, From 0.2 to 3.25 mol kg⁻¹ Ionic Strength and from 5 °C To 45 °C

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1. INTRODUCTION

The oceans absorb approximately 25–30% of the carbon dioxide (CO₂) emitted by human activities, driving a progressive shift in seawater chemistry known as ocean acidification [1]. When CO₂ dissolves in seawater it reacts with water to form carbonic acid, which dissociates to release hydrogen ions, lowering seawater pH. Since pre-industrial times, mean ocean surface pH has declined by approximately 0.1 units on the total pH scale – from around 8.2 to 8.1 – a change that, because the pH scale is logarithmic, corresponds to a roughly 26% increase in hydrogen ion

concentration [2]. Elevated [H⁺] shifts the carbonate equilibrium, reducing the saturation state of aragonite and calcite (the mineral forms of calcium carbonate used by corals, molluscs, and many planktonic organisms) with serious consequences for marine biodiversity, fisheries productivity, and the biological carbon pump [2,3].

Reliable detection of the trend in seawater pH demands measurements of the highest metrological quality: the anticipated rate of change is approximately 0.002 pH units per year, placing stringent requirements on measurement uncertainty, long-term reproducibility, and inter-laboratory comparability. Underpinning

assessments of the effects of reduced pH with measurements traceable to the *SI* is therefore not merely a technical goal but a prerequisite for the robust, policy-relevant science needed to monitor and respond to ocean acidification.

The IUPAC definition of pH [4] is:

$$\text{pH} = -\log_{10}(a\text{H}^+) = -\log_{10}(m\text{H}^+ \cdot \gamma\text{H}^+ / m^\circ) \quad (1)$$

where $a\text{H}^+$ is the activity of the hydrogen ion, $m\text{H}^+$ its molality (moles per kg of pure water solvent), γH^+ its molal activity coefficient, and m° the standard molality of 1 mol kg⁻¹. Because the activity coefficient of a single ionic species is thermodynamically unmeasurable, that is to say it cannot be separated from the activity coefficients of accompanying counter-ions without an extra-thermodynamic assumption, the operational realisation of this definition requires a convention. The accepted approach, embodied in the IUPAC primary method using Harned cells, adopts the Bates–Guggenheim convention for the activity coefficient of the chloride ion in the buffer solutions used to calibrate the scales. However, its validity is confined to solutions with ionic strength of up to about 0.1 mol kg⁻¹. Seawater, with an ionic strength of approximately 0.7 mol kg⁻¹, lies far beyond this limit. Consequently, the IUPAC primary pH scale cannot be reliably adopted for the measurement of seawater. Instead, the seawater total pH scale (pH_T) is used [5,6]:

$$\text{pH}_T = -\log_{10}([\text{H}^+] + [\text{HSO}_4^-]) \quad (2)$$

where brackets $[\]$ indicate concentrations in units of moles per kg of seawater. The reasons for this apparently unusual definition are described further below. The pH_T scale is calibrated using solutions of artificial seawater in which some Na^+ is replaced by equal molalities of the substance “Tris” (2-amino-2-hydroxymethyl-1,3-propanediol, CAS 77-86-1), and its protonated form TrisH^+ . The most widely used calibration of the scale is that of DelValls and Dickson [7], for practical salinities from 20 to 40 and temperatures between 0 and 45 °C.

Ocean scientists presently use these solutions of Tris buffer in artificial seawater, whose total pH has been assigned using Harned cell measurements as a *primary standard buffer*, to calibrate both pH cells and indicator dyes for use in total pH measurements by spectrophotometry.

The metrological challenges of seawater pH have been discussed by Dickson et al. [6], and there are

several pressing research problems to be addressed:

- Assumptions made in the calibration of the total pH scale that are desirable to quantify in order to link the scale more directly to the *SI*.
- Extension of the scale to high pressures, to facilitate direct total pH measurements in the deep ocean.
- Conversion between total pH and the free pH scale ($\text{pH}_F = -\log_{10}([\text{H}^+])$) used by solid state ocean pH sensors [8].

The collaboration in this CITAC award paper is part of a larger group activity that also involves scientists at the National Metrology Institute of Japan (NMIJ), the National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) in the USA, and others. Our aim is to address the above problems in a multi-year project to develop a chemical thermodynamic model, based upon the Pitzer equations [9], to calculate directly acid base equilibria and species molalities in artificial seawaters containing Tris buffers and improve the metrology of total pH. Our paper in *J. Chem. Eng. Data* describes one of the key sets of measurements required to develop this model.

2. HARNED CELLS

This method of thermodynamic measurement is central to our efforts to obtain the data needed to develop the model. The Harned cell is a hydrogen electrode–silver/silver chloride cell without liquid junction, of the form:

whose cell potential E is given by:

$$E = E^\circ - (RT/F) \ln(m\text{H}^+ \cdot m\text{Cl}^- \cdot \gamma\text{H}^+ \cdot \gamma\text{Cl}^- / m^\circ) \quad (3)$$

where E° is the standard electrode potential of the $\text{Ag}|\text{AgCl}$ electrode, R is the gas constant, T is temperature, and F is the Faraday constant. Because the cell contains no liquid junction, there are no junction potential contributions to E , making it the closest practical realisation of a thermodynamically rigorous electrochemical measurement. Values of the standard potential are obtained by measuring solutions of 0.01 mol kg⁻¹ pure aqueous HCl for which HCl activity coefficients have been determined [10]. Figure 1 shows the half-cells containing the two electrodes in one of the cells at the national metrology

institute of Germany (Physikalisch-Technische Bundesanstalt, or PTB).

In solutions containing HCl together with one or more background salts, for example NaCl or MgCl₂, or mixtures designed to mimic the major ion composition of seawater, the cell potential yields the product $m\text{H}^+ \cdot m\text{Cl}^- \cdot \gamma\text{H}^+ \cdot \gamma\text{Cl}^-$ directly. This is the basis of the measurements in our study.

The calibration of the total pH of Tris buffers in artificial seawater is a more complex procedure and involves the following steps: (i) the measurement of cell potentials of artificial seawater acidified by HCl at different temperatures and salinities; (ii) their extrapolation to zero added HCl to obtain standard cell potentials E^{ox} ; (iii) the combination of these standard

potentials with measured potentials (E) in the Tris buffers (at the same salinities and temperatures) to yield total pH [7]. The compositions of artificial seawater containing the Tris buffer, and pure artificial seawater (at the same practical salinity), differ very slightly due to the presence of the buffer and this introduces an uncertainty into the determined total pH. Despite this, it is believed that the total scale can be calibrated with greater accuracy and lower uncertainty than a free or activity-based pH.

A diagram of a complete Harned cell, including the pre-saturators to equilibrate the flowing H₂ gas with water, is shown in Figure 1 of our paper. Below we show a picture of the parts of a Harned cell that contain the hydrogen and chloride electrodes.

Figure 1. A close-up of parts of a Harned cell at PTB. The grey rounded shape on the left is the chloride electrode, immersed in the measurement solution in a tube that is joined at the bottom (with a capillary tube) to a second tube filled with the same solution and the hydrogen electrode (the dark square shape). A bubble of H₂ gas can be seen. The other parts of the glassware at the right include the pre-saturator for the H₂ gas stream.

3. OUR MEASUREMENTS OF TRIS BUFFERS IN COMPONENTS OF ARTIFICIAL SEAWATER

The composition of a typical salinity 35 artificial seawater including Tris buffer is shown in Figure 2. The chemical thermodynamic model of the Tris buffers that we aim to develop uses the Pitzer equations [9] for the estimation of activity coefficients of the solute species and solvent water. It contains parameters for the following types of interactions between solute species:

1. Cations and anions.

2. Dissimilar ions of the same charge type (e.g., H⁺ and Na⁺), and one of opposite charge type (e.g., H⁺, Na⁺, and Cl⁻).

3. Neutral species, in our case Tris, and individual cations and anions (e.g., Tris with Na⁺) based on a convention such as that the interaction with Cl⁻ is zero.

The values of the parameters are determined by fitting to appropriate thermodynamic data, such as the HCl activity products obtained in our Harned cell measurements. Errors and uncertainties of Pitzer parameters currently available for Tris

buffers in artificial seawater, and new measurements needed, are discussed in detail by Humphreys et al. [11] and Clegg et al. [12].

Figure 2. Molalities of major species in a 0.04 *m* equimolal TrisH⁺/Tris buffer in artificial seawater of nominal practical salinity 35. Ion TrisH⁺ is substituted for an equal molality of Na⁺ thus preserving ionic strength. Composition is largely Na⁺ and Cl⁻, with smaller amounts of Mg²⁺ and SO₄²⁻. Minor acid-base species and ion pairs (H⁺, HSO₄⁻, OH⁻, MgOH⁺) are omitted.

A key characteristic of the Pitzer model, which determines the measurements we are making, is that the interactions that influence the calculated activity coefficients most strongly are those with ions present at the highest molalities. In artificial seawater this is clearly the ions Na⁺ and Cl⁻. Consequently, Harned cell measurements of potentials in solutions of NaCl containing equimolal TrisHCl and Tris are of high priority for model development. They are the subject of our paper.

Our primary results are tabulations of measured cell potentials in solutions of NaCl containing added equimolal Tris and salt TrisHCl, for total Cl⁻ molalities from 0.20 to 3.25 mol kg⁻¹ and from 5 to 45 °C. The values of the standard potentials, E° in equation 3, were also determined. We did not fit Pitzer model parameters such as those for TrisH⁺-Cl⁻ or Tris-Na⁺ interactions from the measurements because this will be done in the future from a larger combined dataset that includes both literature

data and measurements yet to be made by members of our collaboration.

Figure 3. Values of the acidity function Q (on a decadal logarithmic basis) at 25 °C plotted against the square root of ionic strength (I). Open symbols – all data from our paper; solid squares – results of Maksimov et al. [13]; dots – calculated from measured cell potentials of DelValls and Dickson [7] for salinities 20 to 40. Dotted line – model calculation for 25 °C [12].

In Figure 3 we compare values of an acidity function Q at 25 °C obtained from our measurements with two other sets of values: those determined by NMIJ for solutions of the same composition [13], and also for an artificial seawater containing the buffer [7]. The acidity function is given by:

$$Q = \ln(m\text{H}^+ \cdot \gamma\text{HCl}^2) = (E^\circ - E) \cdot (\text{FIRT}) - \ln(m\text{Cl}^-) \quad (4)$$

where E is the measured potential, E° is the measured standard cell potential, and the molality $m\text{Cl}^-$ is known. The quantity γHCl is the mean activity coefficient of HCl, equal to $(\gamma\text{H}^+ \cdot \gamma\text{Cl}^-)^{0.5}$.

The results for the NaCl medium agree quite well with those for artificial seawater (as expected, given the dominance of NaCl), and also with the draft Pitzer model of the complete solution constructed by Clegg et al. [12]. This is encouraging.

4. LESSONS FOR THE FUTURE

Working Harned cells are now found almost exclusively in national metrology laboratories, where they are used to certify standard pH buffer solutions for the chemical industry. These buffer solutions are all relatively dilute (below about 0.1 mol kg^{-1}), and the protocols developed for electrode preparation, storage, and reuse, reflect this fact. When used *only* for the measurement of dilute solutions the Cl^- electrodes may last for many years. This contrasts with the standard practice of Bates for example, and of Dickson, to prepare fresh electrodes for each set of measurements (Dickson, pers. comm.). We have found in our collaboration (including measurements carried out at NMIJ and at NIST) that chloride electrode degradation is accelerated in solutions containing high molalities of Cl^- , which has the effect of introducing offsets in the standard potentials. The reason for this is that the solubility of AgCl in aqueous solutions *increases* with total Cl^- molality due to complex formation [14]. Fresh electrodes therefore appear to be essential for measuring such solutions.

The preparation of hydrogen and chloride electrodes is described in the text book of Bates [16], but there are some small differences in

procedures used by the different NMIs. In order to encourage the future more widespread use of Harned cells for HCl activity product measurements we have been careful to describe electrode preparation at PTB in detail, and also other aspects of the processing of the raw Harned cell potentials (mainly to adjust them to exactly $1 \text{ atm } p\text{H}_2$). Similar descriptions can be found in the Supporting Information to the work of Maksimov et al. [15] which also contains comments by Andrew Dickson that describe procedures in his laboratory at the Scripps Institution of Oceanography where different.

5. OUR COLLABORATION

The experimental programme needed to quantify all the Tris buffer – artificial seawater interactions in the model of the buffers is large, and involves several institutions and international projects and working groups, see Figure 4 below. The work described in our paper is a contribution to this. Laboratory measurements in support of model development have been made by all organisations in categories 2 and 4.

Figure 4. The timeline and main organisations participating in the development chemical speciation models of seawater and the Tris buffers used to calibrate the seawater total pH scale. Abbreviations: GEOMAR - Helmholtz Centre for Ocean Research Kiel; SCOR – the Scientific Committee for Oceanic Research; JCS – the Joint Committee on the Properties of Seawater; UN Ocean Decade project – the Marine Chemistry Speciation Group “MarChemSpec”.

The research of PTB on seawater pH began in 2011, when their electrochemistry laboratory joined a European Metrology Research Programme project “*Metrology for ocean salinity and acidity*” on the establishment of a metrological basis for essential oceanographic parameters like salinity, temperature, density, conductivity, pH value, oxygen concentration and composition. This project involved twelve European partners. Since then, there have been several follow-up projects and collaborations aimed at improving the determination of especially seawater total pH (pH_T) and its traceability to higher order standards and ultimately to the *SI*.

Author Frank Bastkowski was an associate member of SCOR Working Group 145 “*Chemical Speciation Modelling in Seawater to Meet 21st Century Needs*”, which was formed in 2015 to document and implement state-of-the-art Pitzer models of chemical speciation in seawater and related solutions. Representatives of the national metrology institutes of Japan and France also joined as associate members in order to provide measurements to establish chemical speciation models of Tris buffers in artificial seawater, and thereby support improved traceability of total pH to the *SI*. Author Simon Clegg was the Vice-Chair and a founding member of Working Group 145, which now continues as a UN Ocean Decade project focused on marine chemical speciation (“MarChemSpec”).

The work described in our paper was carried out at PTB in December 2020 and January 2021, and is the third publication in our planned series of Harned cell measurements in support of the model of Tris buffers. This programme is ongoing at both PTB and NMIJ. A further three year project to quantify pressure effects on buffer properties has recently begun, with research funding from the UK and USA, under the leadership of Simon Clegg. This work is a BIPM recommendation [17].

6. CONCLUSION

The work that is the subject of this CITAC award is a part of a large collaboration between national metrology institutes and academic scientists, focused on improved metrology of pH determination in seawater. The collaboration makes use of the unique Harned cell measurement capabilities of the national metrology laboratories

and combines this with academic experience in the development of chemical speciation models in order to address problems in the metrology of seawater total pH. The overall project is ambitious and will take some time to realise its final result, which is a speciation model of Tris buffers in artificial seawater for the calculation of total and free pH and with quantified uncertainties.

We are grateful for the support of our funders, the commitment of the national metrology institutes of Germany, Japan and the USA, and the encouragement of the BIPM.

APPENDIX. USE OF HARNED CELLS AT PTB

Harned cells have been in use at PTB since the early 1990s. The pH measurement procedure using the Harned cell is a so-called primary reference measurement procedure, meaning it can be used to determine the pH value of a primary pH standard without reference to a higher-order measurement standard for pH.

At PTB, the Harned cell is mainly used to certify standard pH buffer solutions for commercial customers. In order to ensure international comparability of the pH measurement results PTB is a member of the Working Group for Electrochemical Analysis of the Consultative Committee for the Amount of Substance (CCQM) and takes part in interlaboratory pH measurements within the scope of the Mutual Recognition Arrangement of the International Committee for Weights and Measures (CIPM-MRA, see <https://www.bipm.org/en/cipm-mra>).

The Harned cells at PTB were built not only to provide calibration services but also for research purposes, such as the determination of the total pH of Tris buffers as described above. In our study the cells provide thermodynamic data – the activity products of H^+ and Cl^- ions – to be used to develop chemical speciation models that will ultimately improve the metrology of the buffers and enable the extension of the total pH scale to a wider range of conditions.

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CITAC BEST PAPERS AWARD 2025

On the Role of Probability in Science, Analytical Measurement and QUAM

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Abstract

Recently, it has been shown that a probability distribution attributed to a constant, e.g., the true concentration of an analyte, cannot be used to accurately describe an objective set of information about the constant (Measurement Sensors 24, 2022, 100416; Accreditation and Quality Assurance 29, 2024, 189–192). In this paper, that result is extended to show that such a distribution cannot always accurately describe subjective belief about it either. These results suggest that a logical system of uncertainty analysis in measurement can only be based on classical principles in which probability distributions describe patterns of measurements and errors under repetition. They call into question the premise underlying the approach to the evaluation of measurement uncertainty promoted in the supplements to the *Guide to the Expression of Uncertainty in Measurement*. The relevance of these results to the Eurachem/CITAC Guide *Quantifying Uncertainty in Analytical Measurement* (QUAM) is discussed, and QUAM is shown to be largely free of the problematic idea.

1 Introduction

Recent articles [1]–[3] have considered the controversial idea that a probability distribution can be attributed to an unknown constant, such as the true value of the measurand, θ . Willink [1] showed that if two probability distributions could accurately encode two separate sets of information about θ then, on uniting those sets of information, there would be conflicting probability distributions for the quantity $\lambda \equiv g(\theta)$ when g is monotonic and non-linear, as with the simple quantity $\lambda = 1/\theta$. The only logical conclusion to draw was that, in general, *a probability distribution cannot accurately encode a set of information about an unknown constant*. This result, if correct, has severe implications for an ‘objective Bayesian’ view of data analysis. The present communication shows how the analysis that led to that result can be extended to apply to the subjective Bayesian understanding of probability also. We are led to the conclusion that a continuous probability distribution attributed to a constant does not necessarily satisfy the principles of logic, no matter how it is interpreted.

From this conclusion, it follows that the *Guide to the Expression of Uncertainty in Measurement* (GUM) [4,5] should not be interpreted in such a way: however, this is the case in recent supplementary material to the GUM, e.g., [6,7]. Rather, any interpretation or extension of the GUM must follow classical lines. This issue is relevant to the Eurachem/CITAC Guide “Quantifying Uncertainty in Analytical Measurement” (QUAM) [8], which describes a method of analysis that is consistent with a classical reading of the (original) GUM, but which contains some peripheral clauses that appeal to the problematic concept.

Section 2 demonstrates the result for objective probability and Section 3 extends the result to apply to subjective probability. Section 4 briefly discusses the position taken in official documents that have been developed to build on the GUM, and Section 5 examines in more detail the contrasting approach taken in QUAM, upholding that approach but providing cautionary comments.

2 Analysis for distributions representing information about constants

The objective Bayesian position in which probability represents “rational belief” is based on

the following premise. “From any set of information, i.e., set of facts, relating to a quantity, there is a unique pdf to attribute to that quantity”, e.g., [9, pp. 9,10]. So let us imagine that unknown constant quantities θ_1 and θ_2 exist, that you accept the premise, and that you attribute probability density functions (pdfs) $f_1(x)$ and $f_2(x)$ to θ_1 and θ_2 to accurately represent disjoint sets of information about them, say the sets S_1 and S_2 . Let $\hat{\theta}_1$ and $\hat{\theta}_2$ be the values of θ_1 and θ_2 when rounded onto a discrete scale with potential values $\dots -2\delta, -\delta, 0, \delta, 2\delta, \dots$, and let $p_1(x)$ and $p_2(x)$ be the corresponding probability mass functions (pmfs). (So $p_j(x) = \int_{x-\delta/2}^{x+\delta/2} f_j(z) dz$.) Then, in your thinking, $\hat{\theta}_1$ and $\hat{\theta}_2$ are independent discrete random variables with pmfs $p_1(x)$ and $p_2(x)$, these variables being independent because the sets of information that they describe, S_1 and S_2 , are disjoint. The corresponding joint pmf is

$$\Pr(\hat{\theta}_1 = x_1 \cap \hat{\theta}_2 = x_2) = p_1(x_1)p_2(x_2).$$

This is exemplified in Figure 1(a) for $\delta = 1$ with $(p_1(2), p_1(3), p_1(4), p_1(5), p_1(6)) = (0.2, 0.3, 0.2, 0.2, 0.1)$, $(p_2(1), p_2(2), p_2(3), p_2(4), p_2(5)) = (0.1, 0.2, 0.2, 0.4, 0.1)$.

Figure 1: (a) Example joint probability mass function $\Pr(\hat{\theta}_1 = x_1 \cap \hat{\theta}_2 = x_2)$ with $\delta = 1$. (b) Corresponding probability mass function on the condition that $\hat{\theta}_1 = \hat{\theta}_2$. (Empty cells have mass zero).

Recall that the probability that event A occurs on the condition that event B occurs is

$$\Pr(A|B) = \frac{\Pr(A \cap B)}{\Pr(B)}. \quad (1)$$

Now suppose that you receive the single new piece of information that θ_1 and θ_2 are equal, which is a single piece of information constituting a set S_3 . So you learn that $\hat{\theta}_1$ and $\hat{\theta}_2$ are equal. On the condition that $\hat{\theta}_1 = \hat{\theta}_2$, the probability that $\hat{\theta}_1$ and $\hat{\theta}_2$ have different values is zero and the probability that $\hat{\theta}_1$ and $\hat{\theta}_2$ are equal to any dummy figure x is seen to be

$$\Pr(\hat{\theta}_1 = \hat{\theta}_2 = x | \hat{\theta}_1 = \hat{\theta}_2) = \frac{p_1(x)p_2(x)}{\sum_z p_1(z)p_2(z)}, \quad (2)$$

which is a quantity that involves only the diagonal elements of the array of joint probabilities, as depicted in Figure 1(b) for the unconditional distribution of Figure 1(a). There is now only one unknown quantity, which we can rename θ , with the discretized form being $\hat{\theta}$. We find that, after this new piece of information has been accommodated, you must regard $\hat{\theta}$ as a discrete random variable with pmf

$$p(x) = \frac{p_1(x)p_2(x)}{\sum_z p_1(z)p_2(z)}. \quad (3)$$

It makes no difference to your final set of information about $\hat{\theta}$ whether you learn that $\hat{\theta}_1$ and $\hat{\theta}_2$ are equal before or after you are provided with the two sets of information S_1 and S_2 , i.e., it makes no difference to your final set of information $S_{\text{final}} \equiv S_1 \cup S_2 \cup S_3$ whether you receive S_3 first or last. So (3) must also represent the correct combination of pmfs $p_1(x)$ and $p_2(x)$ that are said to correspond to two disjoint sets of information about a single quantity, $\hat{\theta}$.

Equation (3) can be written as

$$\frac{p(x)}{\delta} = \frac{p_1(x)/\delta \times p_2(x)/\delta}{\sum_z p_1(z)/\delta \times p_2(z)/\delta \times \delta'}$$

and this equation holds whatever the value of the unit of resolution, δ . As δ is reduced to zero, $\hat{\theta}$ becomes θ , $p_j(\cdot)/\delta$ becomes $f_j(\cdot)$, $p(\cdot)/\delta$ becomes a combined pdf $f(\cdot)$, and the sum becomes an integral. This gives the expression

$$f(x) = \frac{f_1(x)f_2(x)}{\int f_1(z)f_2(z) dz} \quad (4)$$

as the unique equation describing the result when two independently-formed objective pdfs $f_1(x)$ and $f_2(x)$ for a single constant are to be logically combined.

Let us now use a subscript in the pdf to identify the quantity of interest, e.g., θ . The analysis that has led to (4) has proven the following result: if $f_{1\theta}(x)$ and $f_{2\theta}(x)$ are the pdfs to attribute to a quantity θ to accurately represent two disjoint sets of information about θ then the pdf to accurately represent the union of the sets of information obeys, [1, Sec. 3.2], e.g., [10, Eqs. 5,6][11, Eq. 15]

$$f_{12\theta}(x) \propto f_{1\theta}(x)f_{2\theta}(x). \quad (5)$$

Now suppose that the particular quantity of interest is $\lambda = g(\theta)$, where g is a monotonic function. As is well known, if the pdf attributed to θ is $f_{\theta}(x)$ then the pdf attributed to λ must be

$$f_{\lambda}(y) = f_{\theta}(x) \left| \frac{dx}{dy} \right| \quad y = g(x). \quad (6)$$

So, if there are two disjoint sets of information about θ then the pdf attributable to the transformed quantity λ will logically be found from the input pdfs $f_{1\theta}(x)$ and $f_{2\theta}(x)$ in two stages, with one stage involving the aggregation of information using the combination equation (5) and the other involving the re-representation of information using the transformation equation (6). The application of these equations simply represents logical reasoning with mathematical entities that are said to fully represent separate sets of information, and – just as there is no difference in the result if we traverse a city block by going forward and then sideways or sideways and then forward – there can be no difference in the result if we combine first and then transform or transform first and then combine. Thus, it is legitimate to combine $f_{1\theta}(x)$ and $f_{2\theta}(x)$ into the ensuing single pdf for θ and then transform this to the corresponding pdf for λ , and it is also legitimate to transform $f_{1\theta}(x)$ and $f_{2\theta}(x)$ into the two corresponding pdfs for λ and then combine these into the ensuing single pdf for λ . The result must be the same because all that is apparently being carried out is the aggregation and re-expression of quantifiable information.

Combining the two pdfs before transforming from θ to λ gives the intermediate result (5) and the final pdf

$$f_{12\lambda}(y) \propto f_{1\theta}(x)f_{2\theta}(x) \left| \frac{dx}{dy} \right|, \quad (7)$$

but transforming to λ before combining gives the intermediate result $f_{j\lambda}(y) = f_{j\theta}(x) |dx/dy|$ for $j = 1, 2$ and the final pdf

$$f_{12\lambda}(y) \propto f_{1\theta}(x) f_{2\theta}(x) \left| \frac{dx}{dy} \right|^2, \quad (8)$$

in which the Jacobian $|dx/dy|$ is raised to the power of 2, (because there are two contributing pdfs). The pdfs (7) and (8) differ if g is non-linear, as with the simple relationship $\lambda = 1/\theta$. Yet both are obtained from our premise and from correct use of probability theory. It follows that the premise that a set of information can be accurately encoded as a probability distribution leads to an internal inconsistency [1, Sec. 3.3]. Therefore, this premise must be incorrect. We conclude that a probability distribution for a constant does not accurately represent a *set of information* about it, i.e., a set of facts relating to it. This is the conclusion emphasized in the earlier publications [1,3].

3 Extension to distributions representing subjective belief about constants

Now let us consider whether the assignment of a (continuous) probability distribution to a constant can instead accurately represent *subjective belief* about it. So let $f_{1\theta}(x)$ now be your subjective pdf for an unknown quantity, say the diameter θ of a specific disk. According to Bayesian reasoning, this pdf can be formed by any thought process that you like: all that is required is that it honestly represents your belief about θ based on all that you consider relevant. Suppose that *after* forming $f_{1\theta}(x)$ you are told by some external party that the disk was drawn at random from a production line that created disks with diameters following a frequency distribution with a density $g(x)$. Taken in isolation, this so-far unused impression or piece of information would have led to you to form some pdf of belief, $f_{2\theta}(x)$, from it. (The form of $f_{2\theta}(x)$ is not important to this argument, but surely a person who fully trusted what they had been told would have assigned θ the pdf $f_{2\theta}(x) = g(x)$.) The two pdfs $f_{1\theta}(x)$ and $f_{2\theta}(x)$ are derived from independent (disjoint, separate) influences – and they can also be interpreted as pdfs for two quantities that are subsequently found to be the same, exactly as in the argument in Section 2. So when combining these two pdfs to express your final belief about θ you must form the product $f_{12\theta}(x) \propto f_{1\theta}(x) f_{2\theta}(x)$, as above. Then the same inconsistency arises when, for example, you study the area of the disk $\lambda = \pi\theta^2/4$ as well as its diameter θ .

Thus, we are forced to the conclusion that, in general, attributing a *subjective* probability distribution to a constant also admits a logical contradiction. So, it appears that the basis of Bayesian statistical analysis is illogical. For that conclusion to be denied, the analysis that has just been given must itself be shown to be incorrect.

4 Supplements to the “Guide to the Expression of Uncertainty in Measurement”

The material above might seem academic and irrelevant to those who only use probability for its classical task of describing the frequency behaviour of unpredictable processes. However, current international guidelines in measurement science adopt the position that probability distributions are (also) to be given to constants, as in Bayesian analysis. For example, in a document of 2009 [6, 3.17] that claims to introduce the *Guide to the Expression of Uncertainty in Measurement* (GUM) of 1995 [4, 5] we read

The true values of the input quantities ... are unknown. In the approach advocated, [the input quantities] are characterized by probability distributions ... and treated mathematically as random variables These distributions describe the respective probabilities of their true values lying in different intervals, and are assigned based on available knowledge concerning [the input quantities].

and in the first supplement to the GUM from 2008 we read [7, Introduction]:

The PDF for a quantity expresses the state of knowledge about the quantity, i.e. it quantifies the degree of belief about the values that can be assigned to the quantity based on the available information.

The relevant idea is that a constant, e.g., the true value of the measurand, is being attributed a probability distribution. Accordingly, we can read in related material [12, 3b]

A probability distribution (on the set of possible values of the measurand) provides a complete characterization of measurement uncertainty ...

So, from the analysis given above, we reach the inescapable conclusion that guidelines recently issued to clarify and extend the GUM have adopted a premise that is logically inconsistent. This implies

that they cannot possibly lead to a coherent universal system of analysis. Perhaps more importantly, it means that the system currently advocated by authority for the analysis of measurement uncertainty in science is founded on an unscientific misconception.

5 Eurachem/CITAC Guide – “Quantifying Uncertainty in Analytical Measurement”

Our subject is the notion of attributing a probability distribution to an unknown constant. In the context of metrology, this has been called the ‘distributed measurand’ concept (13), but here we will call it the ‘distributed-constant idea’. It remains to comment on the relationship of this idea to the current edition of QUAM (8). Our conclusion will be that, to a large extent, QUAM avoids the logical error that has been outlined. However, by the peripheral inclusion of some related material, QUAM endangers its scientific position.

Classical and neo-classical ideas

In the context of statistical analysis, QUAM begins with a statement of classical ideas. We read

2.3.3. ... The expanded uncertainty provides an interval within which the value of the measurand is believed to lie with a higher level of confidence.

The use of the word ‘confidence’ implies the adoption of the classical approach, though clearer wording would be ‘is believed with a higher level of confidence to lie’. If the distributed-constant idea had been adopted then the most appropriate word here would have been ‘probability’ and it would have appeared in the phrase ‘is believed to lie with a higher probability’.

So QUAM uses classical language, where the concept of confidence is associated with an interval obtained using a well-defined repeatable procedure. Accordingly we read

2.4.2. Uncertainty, on the other hand, takes the form of a range or interval, and, if estimated for an analytical procedure and defined sample type, may apply to all determinations so described. ...

The fact that uncertainty is assessed *for an analytical procedure* and *for all determinations* places the emphasis on variability in the data-generating process, not on doubt about the specific measurand. So, for QUAM, uncertainty is

primarily determined by the procedure; in contrast, the distributed-constant idea makes the uncertainty a property of the specific measurand. (See QUAM 7.3 where the focus is on procedure.) Also, the fact that uncertainty is said to be ‘estimated’ implies that it is something objective and unknown. (See also QUAM section 4). If the distributed-constant idea applied then the uncertainty would be fully known because it would simply describe one’s own state of mind about the true value of the measurand.

In accordance with these ideas, the distributions that QUAM describes are distributions of data, whether observable in repeatable measurements or unobservable via a concept of belief (8, 7.15.5, 7.15.6), not distributions assigned to constants. Under the heading ‘Estimation based on judgement’, we read

7.15.2. Most distributions of data can be interpreted in the sense that it is less likely to observe data in the margins of the distribution than in the centre. The quantification of these distributions and their associated standard deviations is done through repeated measurements.

and then

7.15.9. For the purpose of estimation of combined uncertainties two features of degree of belief estimations are essential:

- degree of belief is regarded as interval valued which is to say that a lower and an upper bound similar to a classical probability distribution is provided,
- the same computational rules apply in combining ‘degree of belief’ contributions of uncertainty to a combined uncertainty as for standard deviations derived by other methods.

There is no mention of ‘standard deviation’ in the material between these two clauses, so the standard deviations of the degree-of-belief contributions being combined in 7.15.9 are as standard deviations for data (e.g., measurements) in 7.15.2, not as standard deviations describing belief about constants. In keeping with this we read

7.15.7. This may appear to be a disadvantage, but need not lead in practice to worse estimates than those from repeated measurements. This applies

particularly if the true, real-life, variability in experimental conditions cannot be simulated and the resulting variability in data thus does not give a realistic picture.

The quotations that have just been given illustrate the key point: QUAM understands uncertainty to be about variability under repetition, and where actual repetition is not practical it appeals to the concept of degree of belief about variability, not degree of belief about a constant. So, QUAM upholds a degree-of-belief concept, but the subject of the belief is the error in a potential measurement of a fixed measurand: the subject of the belief is not the actual value of that measurand.

This approach is also seen in the next section, which is entitled 'Standard uncertainties'

8.1.2. Where the uncertainty component was evaluated experimentally from the dispersion of repeated measurements, it can readily be expressed as a standard deviation. For the contribution to uncertainty in single measurements, the standard uncertainty is simply the observed standard deviation; for results subjected to averaging, the **standard deviation of the mean ...** is used.

and

8.1.6. Where an estimate is to be made on the basis of judgement, it may be possible to estimate the component directly as a standard deviation. If this is not possible then an estimate should be made of the maximum deviation which could reasonably occur in practice (excluding simple mistakes). If a smaller value is considered substantially more likely, this estimate should be treated as descriptive of a triangular distribution. If there are no grounds for believing that a small error is more likely than a large error, the estimate should be treated as characterising a rectangular distribution.

The phrase "the maximum deviation which could reasonably occur in practice" shows that QUAM has in mind a distribution corresponding to the generation of data (with errors) in a measurement procedure.

So QUAM upholds a degree-of-belief concept for a potential measurement or a potential error in a

measurement, but (in the body of its text) it does not use the degree-of-belief concept employed by Bayesian statisticians, which is the concept that each unknown constant is to be attributed a probability distribution, i.e., the distributed-constant idea.

In this way, QUAM is conceptually consistent with a neo-classical method of analysis recently developed to be true to foundational principles [14], including the report [15] containing Recommendation INC-1 [4, 0.7], where Type B evaluation of uncertainty was formally recommended. (The term 'neo-classical' seems appropriate because the 'Type B' recommendation that variances and probability distributions can be associated with systematic errors constitutes a departure from the classical approach as perceived by statisticians [16].)

5.2 Distributed-constant idea

However, QUAM also briefly refers to some ideas and principles found in the supplements to the GUM, which are inconsistent with the classical ideas above and which we have demonstrated are logically flawed. To show this, we make clear the meaning of the term 'input quantity'. In Clause 4.1, QUAM considers various steps in the problem of assessing the uncertainty in measurement. We read

Step 1. Specify measurand

Write down a clear statement of what is being measured, including the relationship between the measurand and the input quantities (*e.g.* measured quantities, constants, calibration standard values *etc.*) upon which it depends. ...

This confirms that QUAM sees an *input quantity* as having the nature of a measurand, not the nature of a potential measurement. (Indeed, there is explicit mention of constants potentially being input quantities.) So an input quantity has an unknown true value, and to attribute it a probability distribution would be to abandon the classical statistical approach and to adopt the distributed-constant idea. This is relevant, because in Appendix E.3, which is new to the third edition, we then find text that presumes acceptance of the distributed-constant idea. In Clause E.3.2 we read

Monte Carlo Simulation calculates the result corresponding to one value of each input quantity drawn at random from its

PDF, and repeats this calculation a large number of times (trials), typically 10^5 to 10^6 . This process produces a set of simulated results which, under certain assumptions, forms an approximation to the PDF for the value of the measurand. From this set of simulated results, the mean value and standard deviation are calculated. In GUM Supplement 1, these are used respectively as the estimate of the measurand and the standard uncertainty associated with this estimate. ...

We read of input quantities having PDFs, the value of the measurand having a PDF, the mean (of this PDF) being the estimate of the measurand, and the standard deviation (of this PDF) being the corresponding standard uncertainty. So, Appendix E.3 describes the distributed-constant idea, which is not compatible with the classical approach found in the remainder of QUAM. Thus, any positive reference in the body of QUAM to the technique of analysis in Appendix E.3 can only introduce confusion. Moreover, as shown earlier in this article, the distributed-constant idea is not logically sound!

5.3 Comments

This section has demonstrated that the statistical and probabilistic material in the body of QUAM relates to distributions of estimates or distributions of errors in estimates, as was initially envisaged for Type B evaluation [15, 16]. Yet QUAM would claim compatibility with the GUM. So there is evidence that the writers of QUAM and the writers of the supplements to the GUM have interpreted the original GUM differently. The writers of QUAM have (almost entirely) avoided considering the measurand to have a distribution, whereas the writers of the supplements to the GUM, who form Working Group 1 (WG1) of the Joint Committee for Guides in Metrology (JCGM), expressly base their methodology and recommendations upon that idea. In QUAM, a degree-of-belief concept is applied to estimates in a manner that is consistent with a neo-classical form of analysis described recently [14]. But in the material prepared by WG1, the degree-of-belief concept is applied to constants. So if QUAM continues to claim compatibility with the GUM while WG1 continues to produce new material that is said to form part of "the GUM" then QUAM will be seen to be accepting an illogical basis for its system of analysis. This should be a matter of concern.

6 Conclusions

The practice of attributing a probability distribution to an entity to describe belief about it arises in Type B evaluation of measurement uncertainty. But this practice is fundamentally different for parties who consider different types of entity. For those who adhere to a classical or neo-classical approach, the entity will be the future output of a measurement procedure, be it a future datum or the error in the future datum, as was originally envisaged [15]. Then the distribution describing degree-of-belief will be little more than a standard model for the generation of an error, the only difference being an inability to test the model by repetition of the experiment. But for those who adhere to the Bayesian view of statistics, the entity will usually be an unknown constant, as in the distributed-constant idea. So the legitimacy of a 'degree of belief' is not being criticized here: rather, it is the breadth of its applicability.

Accordingly, this paper has built on earlier papers [1,3] to give a succinct demonstration that, in general, attributing a probability distribution to a constant to describe your belief about it admits a logical contradiction. The demonstration appears to invalidate the Bayesian view of data analysis, so it requires acceptance or rebuttal in the community of statisticians and the wider community of applied scientists. It goes some way to explaining how the methodology of the GUM supplements can give strange and unreasonable results, as exemplified in the practical scenario discussed by Hall [17] and in many other simple situations [18, Section 4.3.2].

The result put forward in this paper urgently needs to be disproven if guidelines in metrology are to continue to adopt the premise that probability distributions can be attributed to measurands while claiming to have a logical basis. The guidelines of concern are those prepared by Working Group 1 of the Joint Committee for Guides in Metrology, which has produced a suite of documents claiming to build on the GUM of 1993/1995, e.g., [6, 7]. By and large, the current edition of QUAM avoids the problem and continues to base its method on the classical understanding that probability distributions only relate to the spread of data or observations. A future edition of QUAM should distance itself further from the illogical premise.

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ABOUT CITAC

CITAC – Cooperation on International Traceability in Analytical Chemistry – arose out of an international workshop held in association with the Pittsburgh Conference in Atlanta in March 1993. The aim of this workshop was to discuss how analytical activities could be developed to meet the needs of the 21st century, and it identified a wide variety of issues to be addressed to ensure that analytical measurements made in different countries or at different times are comparable. These range from the development of traceable reference materials and methods to the harmonisation of analytical quality practices.

The CITAC initiative aims to foster collaboration between existing organisation to improve the international comparability of chemical measurement. A Working Group takes matters forward and its initial activities have centred on a few specific high priority activities. The first tasks included the compilation of a directory of certified reference materials under development; preparation of quality system guidelines for the production of reference materials; preparation of a directory of international chemical metrology activities; defining criteria for establishing traceability to the mole; and the preparation of an international guide to quality in analytical chemistry.

Many of these activities are of a strategic nature, laying the ground for the improvement of international analytical measurement. This reflects the added geographical complexities associated with a world-wide organisation, such as greater diversity in culture and in technical approach, and frequently long timescales associated with its activities. Nevertheless, if the full benefits of improved analytical measurement are to be realised internationally, a truly global approach is needed, and there is a clear role for CITAC to play in this respect.

CITAC
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